

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

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2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan (for START)
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
ExCom	START's Executive Committee (WP leaders)
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KoM	Kick-off meeting
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
WP	Work Package
PM	Powder Metallurgy
TEG	ThermoElectric Generators
MTOD	Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable reports on the activity of WP6 “Dissemination and Communication” in the period 1st June 2023 – 30th November 2023¹ (M13-M18 of the START project).

It covers the endeavours within the following tasks (the ones running in said period):

- Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools
- Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination
- Task 6.4: Clustering

Task 6.3 (Training) is also running, but it will be reported in D6.8 in May 2024 (M24), so it is not touched here if not to mention some activities that can also be considered as Dissemination.

The activities for D&C, that are reported in this deliverable, include:

- Updates to the START project website.
- Updates on the Social Media accounts (LinkedIn, YouTube, Twitter, Twitch, SlideShare).
- The third issue of the public biannual newsletter “RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE”.
- The third free webinar, on 31st May 2023, held hybrid in Madrid and online, with about 60 participants.
- Publications (Starty multilingual, an article on the magazine “Ciência & Tecnologia dos Materiais”, etc.).
- Dissemination at events (workshops, congresses and others, in person and online), including some training events (EPMA and SPM Summer Schools).

The KPIs set for the D&C activities have mostly been met (not considering those that have a longer deadline), with the exception of Twitter/X, but some data reassure on a positive impact even on that platform.

The clustering activity has continued in such a way that the database on EU-funded projects, which was created at the beginning of the project, has been updated and completed. Contacts have been initiated with other key projects, stakeholders and organizations engaged in related activities, such as the Fraunhofer Institute for Manufacturing Technology and Advanced Materials IFAM or The Leibniz Institute for Solid State and Materials Research Dresden - IFW Dresden. The START project has joined an existing project clustering initiative (ERHASE), and we have attended the SuperCluster event in Rovaniemi, where more than 20 EU-funded projects related to raw materials were present.

¹ For practical reasons linked to text reviewing and submission, some details related to the last 2 weeks of November could not be reported and will be dealt with in the next deliverable of the same series, D6.7 (M24, May 2024).

4 INTRODUCTION: STRUCTURE OF WP6 AND GENERAL PLAN OF ACTIVITIES

4.1 OBJECTIVES OF WP6

The overall objective of WP6 is to disseminate widely the results of the START project in order to maximise its impact. The key objectives are:

- To raise awareness of all relevant parties (scientific and industrial communities, general public and policy makers) about START project activities in a coherent and consistent manner.
- To ensure an effective dissemination of the technical and scientific results of START project to the scientific and industrial communities.
- To ensure an effective communication of the achievements of START project to the wider scientific and technical communities, policy makers and the general public.
- To elaborate the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) and update it when required.

Various communication activities are envisaged to disseminate the on-going and final project findings:

- Participations in congresses, workshops, webinars
- Training events
- Websites and social media
- Scientific papers
- Newsletters and other publications
- Participation in trade fairs and exhibitions
- Other activities, etc.

All partners are required to collaborate in dissemination and communication by delivering content and executing some dissemination subtasks.

4.2 STRUCTURE OF WP6

4.2.1 Tasks

The activity is organised in 5 Tasks, whose scope and activities will be explained in the main chapters of this report.

- Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools
- Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination
- Task 6.3: Training activities
- Task 6.4: Clustering
- Task 6.5: Final event

The GANTT shows that only Tasks 6.1, 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4 have already begun, whereas Task 6.5 will only run in Year 4, rather close to the end of the project.

Figure 1: GANTT chart for WP6. M01 = June 2022; M48 = May 2026. Bordered in orange, the period covered by this deliverable D6.6.

4.2.2 Deliverables and Milestones

The WP lists 15 deliverables out of a total of 39 for the whole project, but only one milestone, that has already been achieved in M03 (August 2022). The deliverables (all classified as public), also visible in Figure 3, can be grouped in the following categories:

- D6.1 - Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools (M02): This deliverable describes the project's website, addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the START graphical identity, together with all the other online tools designed to support objectives of WP6. *(Submitted and approved)*
- D6.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan (M03): Document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication activities. *(Submitted)*
- D6.3, D6.4, D6.6, D6.7, D6.9, D6.10, D6.12, D6.13 - Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities (M06, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36, M42, M48): Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed. *(D6.6 is the present report, D6.7 upcoming in 6 months)*
- D6.5, D6.8, D6.11, D6.14 - Training activities (M12, M24, M36, M48): Report on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented. *(D6.5 submitted, D6.8 upcoming in 6 months)*
- D6.15 - Final Event (M46): Final event conference report.

Concerning milestones, only one was envisaged, namely Milestone 08:

- MS08: Project Website (M03) - Project website functional and accessible

The website was in fact the key stone of all further dissemination, so it needed to be started as early as possible and was set as a milestone. This milestone has been achieved as planned (declared on 22 August 2022 on the Funding & Tenders Portal, the website being also subject of Deliverable D6.1 submitted earlier and already accepted).

Deliverables												
Work Package No	Deliverable Related No	Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date	Approval Date	Status
WP6	D6.1	D19	Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools	This deliverable describes the project's website, addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the START graphical identity, together with all the other online tools designed to support objectives of WP6.	EPMA	DEC	PU	31 Jul 2022		29 Jul 2022	31 Aug 2022	Approved
WP6	D6.2	D20	Dissemination and Communication Plan	Document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication activities.	EPMA	R	PU	31 Aug 2022		30 Aug 2022		Submitted
WP6	D6.3	D21	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M6	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2022		30 Nov 2022		Submitted
WP6	D6.4	D22	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M12	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2023		31 May 2023		Submitted
WP6	D6.5	D23	Training activities - M12	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2023		31 May 2023		Submitted
WP6	D6.6	D24	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M18	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2023				Pending
WP6	D6.7	D25	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M24	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.8	D26	Training activities - M24	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.9	D27	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M30	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.10	D28	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M36	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.11	D29	Training activities - M36	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.12	D30	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M42	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.13	D31	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M48	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP6	D6.14	D32	Training activities - M48	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP6	D6.15	D33	Final Event	Final event conference report.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 Mar 2026				Pending

To be completed on the current year
 Deadline approaching
 Submitted
 Approved

Figure 2: List of WP6 deliverables, with deadlines and status.

5 TASK 6.1: SPECIFIC PROJECT DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M01 to M48

The objective of this task is to develop tools and produce materials that will be used during and after the project to disseminate the information about the project, its partners, and its results. According to our proposal, these were the items that needed to be developed:

- The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) at the start of the project (described in full in Deliverable D6.2 submitted in August 2022) and updated when required (an update is considered by M24, mid-term).
- Described in Deliverable D6.1 (submitted in July 2022):
 - The Project's Graphical Identity (logo, branding).
 - The START project website.
 - A special area on the EPMA website (www.epma.com) devoted to the START project.
 - Social Media platforms, in particular:
 - A LinkedIn page for networking with the professional community (managed by EPMA).
 - A YouTube profile for engaging with the greater public (managed by EPMA).
 - A Twitter/X account for business and policy makers (managed by LPRC).
 - A Twitch profile for engagement with young people (managed by LPRC).
 - A SlideShare account for disseminating project presentations globally (managed by ASGMI).
- Leaflets, posters, banners, branded consumables that will be used as advertising material to be distributed in digital and/or physical versions.
- A public biannual newsletter to be distributed in digital and/or physical versions.
- A serious game (see WP7, Task 7.1 and deliverable D7.2)
- Videos about the project (2 generic videos, 1 at the start and one at the end, 3 more focused videos on specific topics).

The tools had been further described in the original proposal as in Table 1.

Table 1: Tools for Dissemination and Communication as indicated in the proposal.

Tool	Purpose	Audience	Due	Quantified target
Project Graphical Identity	A Graphical Identity for the START project (logo and general branding colour schemes, for the website, the social media, mail signatures for partners, and all other uses) will be developed in the first months.	All	M02	-
Project website	Main channel for information and major tool for the visibility of the START activities. Updated frequently, with a blend of status, push and active content, including: project overview; public documents; agenda; articles and news; multimedia. Individuals can also use the website to sign up to the newsletter and social media channels.	All groups	M02 onwards	Visitors: 2000 in year 1 rising to at least 4000 in year 4
Social media	LinkedIn, YouTube and Twitter will be considered as main dissemination channels, Slideshare and Twitch as secondary dissemination channels. LinkedIn supports community management with restricted fora. A YouTube channel will be used to engage with a broader audience by sharing videos, including an introduction to START, short interviews, and selected partner videos.	All groups	M02 onwards	Twitter: 1000 followers in year 1, rising to 2500 by the end of the project LinkedIn: 800 followers by the end of the project.
Videos	Some videos are planned for various uses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A short generic video (0.5-1 min) with simple information, to be used for general awareness about START. • A mid-term longer video, highlighting preliminary project results. • 2 or more short videos focused on different subtopics within the project, with examples of improvements achieved within the project. • A short generic video (0.5-1 min) with simple information, to be used as a summary of the results obtained in START. 	Groups 1-4 1-3 2-3 1-4	M04 M24 M48 M48	Average of 200 views per video (at least 100 total views)
Newsletters	A public biannual newsletter will be circulated to individuals who sign up. The newsletter will include a summary of the activities over a 6-month period.	Groups 1-3	M06 onwards	Demand led but minimum of 500 per semester
Webinars/ seminars/ workshop	Communication of the project outcomes and activities, to share knowledge, ideas and updates.	Groups 2, 3	M06 onwards	Audience of 100 per event
Serious online game	A serious online game for capacity building on raw materials, sustainability and circular economy.	All groups	M24 onwards	Visitors: 300
Other publications	Articles on web-based innovation news services, like the Horizon Magazine, Cordis, and on commercial magazines like Open Access Management	All groups	M06 onwards	Total reach >400000

New achievements will be described in the next pages.

5.1 PROJECT WEBSITE

The project's website has been already developed and reported in deliverable D6.1 ("Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools"), submitted on 29th July 2022. It also constituted the criterion for the achievement of Milestone MS08 ("Project Website (M03) - Project website functional and accessible"), that was declared achieved on 22nd August 2022.

The website address is:

www.START-HEproject.com

Another site address, www.HE-START.eu, is automatically redirected to the main address.

The website is continually updated in terms of contents and new features are introduced (new pages, widgets, etc.) if deemed useful.

During the last six months, the period covered by this deliverable, there were no changes in the structure of the website, but some news items, media and documents were added.

On the “Documents” page, the number of available documents for download (Figure 4) raised from 9 to 12 (compare with D6.4). The new additions are:

- “Starty explains START, multilingual edition”, issue #2
- The pdf of the article published on PMR Spring Issue 2023
- The Newsletter Issue #3 (see chapter 5.4.2).

More documents will be made available in the future.

The “News” page is, as always, the page that had more additions. It is the first place where the info about the events and the news about the project are posted (Figure 5). For details it will be useful to consult the website itself, as each piece of news opens a specific page. As an example, we report here only the page about the third video from the START webinar #3 (Figure 6).

The news published are now 20, the latest being the publication of the third edition of the newsletter. In the last period, we published 7:

1. START’s Annual Meeting in Madrid²
2. START Webinar #3, D. Crane’s footage³
3. START Webinar #3, J. Hollis’s footage⁴
4. START Webinar #3, consortium speakers’ footage⁵
5. START LCA workshop footage⁶
6. Starty multilingual #2⁷
7. Newsletter RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE Issue #3⁸

In the Multimedia page (Figure 7), 4 more items are now available:

- START Webinar #3, D. Crane’s footage
- START Webinar #3, J. Hollis’s footage
- START Webinar #3, consortium speakers’ footage
- START LCA workshop footage

The “Consortium” page had to be updated in November 2023 due to the change of logo by the partner BGR (Figure 8). The logo carousel in the Home page was consequently updated too.

² <https://www.start-heproject.com/start-1st-annual-meeting-successfully-run-in-madrid/>

³ <https://www.start-heproject.com/start-webinar-3-watch-doug-cranes-speech-on-thermoelectric-energy-harvesting/>

⁴ <https://www.start-heproject.com/start-webinar-3-watch-julie-hollis-speech-on-the-eus-crm-ambitions-ant-the-role-of-eurogeosurveys/>

⁵ <https://www.start-heproject.com/start-webinar-3-start-partners-share-knowledge-about-tetrahedrites-in-europe/>

⁶ <https://www.start-heproject.com/watch-the-lecture-by-3drivers-on-use-of-lca-for-environmental-impact-assessment/>

⁷ <https://www.start-heproject.com/starty-is-back-in-13-languages/>

⁸ <https://www.start-heproject.com/download-recover-reform-reuse-issue-3-nov-2023/>

Figure 4: Updated Documents page (screenshot taken on 29/11/2023).

Figure 5: The updated News page (screenshot taken on 29/11/2023).

START

Home The Project Documents News Multimedia Consortium CONTACT

The final part of the third START webinar "Sustainable Solutions to Unlock the Potential of Thermoelectrics and Secondary Materials" was dedicated to the investigations that our consortium partners have carried out on the presence of tetrahedrites and other useful sulphides in many European countries, analysing several mine sites and their wastes.

The footage we present you today includes three speeches. **Piotr Lipiarski** (GeoSphere Austria) and **Thomas Unterweissacher** (Unterweissacher) have covered the topic "Tennantite and tetrahedrite from two Austrian mine waste sites", **Concepción Fernández Leyva** (IGME-CSIC) talked about "Tetrahedrite Deposits in Spain", and **Stanislav Šoltés** (Štátny geologický ústav Dionýza Štúra) discussed about "Tetrahedrites from Mária Mine, Rožňava, Slovakia". A nice cross section of the situation, indicating the potential for recovery of these sulphides for our project, to transform them into thermoelectric devices. At the end, the speakers held a common Q&A time.

As always, you will find the the video in our Multimedia page, or directly on YouTube!

Share the link to all the colleagues who could be interested in watching this webinar, and keep in touch for the next video from this webinar (coming soon), and next webinars! Have you already subscribed to our mailing list? You can do it right now in our "Contact" page!

Agenda of the 3rd START webinar, 31st May 2023, 14:30-17:00 CEST

- 14:30 Bruno Vicenzi (European Powder Metallurgy Association) and Filipe Neves (LNEG) - Welcome and introduction
- 14:35 Doug Crane (DTP Thermoelectrics, START Scientific Advisory Board) - "Thermoelectric energy harvesting: principles, challenges and opportunities"
- 15:10 Q&A
- 15:20 Julie Hollis (EuroGeoSurveys, START Scientific Advisory Board) - "The role of EuroGeoSurveys in supporting the EU's ambition to boost domestic critical raw materials supply from secondary resources including mine waste"
- 15:55 Q&A
- 16:05 António José (Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe) - "Sulphidic mining waste in Germany"
- 16:15 Piotr Lipiarski (GeoSphere Austria) and Thomas Unterweissacher (Unterweissacher) - "Tennantite and tetrahedrite from two Austrian mine waste sites"
- 16:25 Concepción Fernández Leyva (IGME-CSIC) - "Tetrahedrite Deposits in Spain"
- 16:35 Stanislav Šoltés (Štátny geologický ústav Dionýza Štúra) - "Tetrahedrites from Mária Mine, Rožňava, Slovakia"
- 16:45 Q&A
- 17:00 End of webinar

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Figure 6: The News item about the third video from the START webinar #3.

Figure 7: The updated Multimedia page.

Laboratorio Nacional de Energia e Geologia I.P. (PT) - Coordinator	https://www.lneg.pt/
3 Drivers - Engenharia, Inovação E Ambiente Lda (PT)	https://www.3drivers.pt/
Asociacion De Servicios De Geologia Y Minería Iberoamericanos (ES)	https://asgmi.org/
Bundesanstalt Für Geowissenschaften Und Rohstoffe (DE)	https://www.bgr.bund.de/
European Powder Metallurgy Association AISBL (BE)	https://www.epma.com/
GeniCore Sp. Z. o.o. (PL)	https://genicore.eu/
Geo Unterweissacher GmbH (AT)	https://www.geo-unterweissacher.at/
Geosphere Austria (AT)	https://www.geologie.ac.at/
La Palma Research Centre SL (ES)	https://www.lapalmacentre.eu/
MBN Nanomaterialia Spa (IT)	https://www.mbn.it/
RGS Development BV (NL)	https://www.rgsdevelopment.nl/
Stratny Geologický Ústav Dionýza Stúra (SK)	https://www.geology.sk/
Sintef AS (NO)	https://www.sintef.no/
TEGnology ApS (DK)	https://www.tegnology.dk/
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Científicas (ES)	https://www.csic.es/

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[Twitter](#) [LinkedIn](#) [YouTube](#) [Instagram](#)

Figure 8: The updated Consortium page.

5.2 EPMA NEWSLETTERS

EPMA publishes regular newsletters for its members and for interested contacts. These are containing at least the link to the START website (typically in the weekly E-Mail newsletters distributed to more than 1600 member contacts and in a reduced version to 400+ non-member contacts), if not specific pieces of news. The latter case happened with the periodic (quarterly) EPMA Newsletter issues. Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the text included in EPMA’s quarterly newsletter #128, distributed in July 2023, and #129, distributed in November 2023, respectively.

[View in browser](#)

Weekly News

 @Euro_PM @europm2023
www.europm2023.com

EPMA News

Replay our Free HM Webinar

Watch our recent HM Webinar on the 100 year development of Hard Materials.

[Read More >](#)

Registration for Young Engineers 2023 Now Open

Register to take part in the event at Euro PM2023 ahead of the 1 July Deadline

[Read More >](#)

Industry News

ASL Course On Atomization For Metal Powders

On 28th and 29th September Atomising Systems will hold the 15th presentation of the intensive two-day course of Atomization of Metals in Manchester, UK.

[Read More >](#)

Study offers insight into vibration-assisted drilling of AM parts

IFT at TU Wien, and research company Fotec have confirmed through joint investigation that vibration-assisted drilling can be successfully applied to AM components.

[Read More >](#)

New mixer for small volumes

Retsch has introduced a new mixer mill which it says can be used for dry, wet and cryogenic grinding of small sample volumes.

[Read More >](#)

START Project Newsletter Issue #2

The START newsletter is back, with plenty new information about our project and the issues we care about!

[Read More >](#)

EPMA Projects

START Project

[Read More >](#)

ADDress Project

[Read More >](#)

Upcoming Events

MIM Seminar 2023
Taking place this week!

[Read More >](#)

Summer School
Fully Reserved

[Read More >](#)

Euro PM2023
Registration Now Open

[Read More >](#)

EPMA
1 avenue du General de Gaulle, 60500, Chantilly

This email was sent to ac@epma.com
You've received this email because you've subscribed to our newsletter.

[Unsubscribe](#)

Sent with

Figure 9: Content of the EPMA weekly newsletter of 23rd May 2023, with the link to the post on the START website concerning the newsletter (Issue 2) and the usual link to the project website.

Club & EU Projects

Club Projects

DPS2 - Completed

The "Desire for Sintering" phase 2 project (DPS2), to develop a model to predict anisotropy by sintering of uniaxially pressed parts, held its final meeting in Trentino on 17th May 2023. Project partners were thoroughly informed about the results of the project that in the second part of its activity was focused on the role of porosity on anisotropy in the mechanisms determining the anisotropy in the compaction plane. The partners expressed satisfaction about the work carried out and the model developed will now be used and further validated during their own day-to-day commercial activities.

Some of these results will be communicated at Euro-PM2023, an international event titled "Desire for Sintering 2 (DPS2) Project" on the topic of dimensional changes in the compaction plane as affected by compaction anisotropy, currently being peer-reviewed by the Technical Programme Committee.

Allowind - Proposal

A proposal for a new club project has been prepared during the sectoral group meeting of EuroHM at WorldPM by Johannes Baetschle (Fraunhofer IPTS) and Jose Manuel Sanchez (CEIT). The objective is to study the influence of binder droplet in hand-moulded thin properties. If you have an interest in joining this new project, please contact Kenan Dogantekin at kenan.dogantekin@epma.eu for further details.

Being responsible for the Dissemination and Communication activities, EPMA was especially active in the last months in preparing the second issue of the project's newsletter, "RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE", that everyone is invited to download for free from the project's website.

Another action was the START webinar series: after the first 2 events, a third webinar was organised on 31st May during the Project's Annual Meeting, hosted from 30th May to 1st June in Madrid in the premises of IGME-CSIC inside the Museo Geominero. It was held in a hybrid format, with the START consortium members onsite in Madrid, and more than 30 participants connected remotely.

During next months, further dissemination will happen in many events, and START will have again its own booth at the Euro PM2023 in Lisbon.

If you are interested in the project, check out its website www.START-HProject.com, and find out more; you can follow also on Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, etc. Subscribing to the mailing list on the website will allow to receive directly news about the project, and in particular the newsletter, whose third issue is expected in October 2023.

European Projects

START's first year was completed

The Horizon Europe project START ("Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling"), dealing with thermoelectric materials made from mine waste minerals and to be used in waste heat recovery devices, has completed its first year of activity.

Most technical activities in the first year were focused on the geology side, especially selecting, visiting and exploring (with sampling included) mine sites that contain tetrahedrites (the sulphides that the project intends to use to produce novel thermoelectric elements). Samples have been characterised, and on some of them a preliminary activity aimed at concentrating tetrahedrites from the ore was undertaken; that is carried out in the powder form. Some interesting results were obtained, and in the future the PM route (and a casting route) will be used to prepare actual thermoelectric samples and assess their performance.

SAM Project

After an intensive 6 months in December 2022, the SAM project had its final meeting on 30th May. The meeting was hosted by Ecole Centrale de Nantes (France) from 30th May to the 1st June, being focused on the presentation of the proposals and the testing plans for the sustainability of the European AM observatory, the European Skills Strategy Roadmap for 2023 and for delivering the AM400 Qualification Courses. The project was coordinated by European Federation for Welding, Joining and Cutting (EFWJ) and the partners were EPMA, CEIM, ITC, Tecnalia, Fraunhofer IPTS and TU Berlin, University London, LTH Laser Akademie GmbH, IK4 Lortek, ISO, IDIVAL, FAN3D, ANSYS, Materialise, IMR Irish Manufacturing Research, ADTIP, Centro Tecnológico - ITC manufacturing Technology Centre.

Address

The Erasmus+ project ADDRESS has been developed to support the building of a Europe-wide training zone by using digital tools and will enable the development of experts professionals and NETEs with a life-long learning perspective. The second Transnational meeting of the project was organised by the Royal Spanish Association of Welding and joining technologies on 30th May in the premises of the consortium. The curriculum included an 8 simulated but compact curriculum for AM training with three levels as Beginner, Intermediate and Advanced. EPMA will lead the task of preparability of Advanced course lectures on Standards and Best Practices for Additive Manufacturing.

Figure 10: EPMA Newsletter #128, July 2023, page 6.

EU Projects

European Projects

RESQTOOL
A new EU funded project in Horizon Europe programme will be launched with a kick-off meeting on 13 December at EPMA offices in Torino. The RESQTOOL consortium is coordinated by EPMA and offers a sustainable alternative for the production of high-end and expensive grade of Critical Raw Materials (Co, W, In, Ti, Nb) from Fe-L products in Hard Metal industries of metal wood cutting, construction and tool manufacturing by lowering the carbon footprint and energy consumption of the current production processes. The project is based on a metal (In, Bi, Sb) chemical recycling based on agro-industrial waste. The consortium consists of 12 partners and the duration is 4 years.

Address
The ADDRESS project had a project meeting in Bologna, Italy, hosted by University of Bologna on the dates of 1-3 October. The consortium worked on the structure of an e-Course in adult that will be used to train workers in 60 companies and SME programmes so that they can acquire working knowledge. Manufacturing advisor, immediately was conducted in Dresden as an Erasmus+ project coordinated by GEFAR, a London foundation (CEVI) in Turkey.

EPMA for new projects
EPMA's technical managers are always actively working for the next EPMA funded projects, like Horizon Europe, Erasmus and others. If you are planning to be more actively participating on a topic, EPMA can already be your partner for Dissemination, coordination and more. Do not hesitate to contact our technical managers Kenan Bozhanaliev (kenan.bozhanaliev@epma.europa.eu) and Bruno L'Hevedec (bruno.lhevedec@epma.europa.eu).

A lecture on START by A. Bianchin (MBN Nanomaterialia) was given to the trainees in the 21st EPMA Summer School in Dresden, in July. J.B. Correia (LNEG) presented the project in the 2nd Summer School "Materials for Energy Transition" organised in Porto (Portugal) by the Portuguese Materials Society.

A third issue of the project's newsletter, "RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE", is being edited right now; please check on our communications and on the project website to download it for free.

START was also present in some geology meetings and will do more presentations in the next weeks (for instance in the European Union SuperCluster Lapland Geoconference in Rovaniemi, Finland, on 30-31 October), and was introduced to the public in some regions in the latest "Researchers night" on 29th September.

START was again exhibiting in Euro PM with its own booth in Lisbon, and J.B. Correia (LNEG) first explained the project to some groups of Young Engineers visiting the exhibition, then held a presentation in the SIS "Sustainability of Critical Raw Materials by PM" held on Tuesday 3 October.

START is well into its second year

The activity within the Horizon Europe project START ("Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling"), dealing with thermoelectric materials made from mine waste minerals (sulfides like the tetrahedrites) and to be used in waste heat recovery devices, is pushing on, and so is EPMA's effort to communicate and disseminate it.

After collecting minerals from mine sites in many European countries (Portugal, Spain, Slovakia, Austria and Germany, proving that tetrahedrites are really available in multiple locations), these minerals have been successfully concentrated and samples of thermoelectric materials with different compositions, modified to boost properties, have been prepared via the powder metallurgical route. The assessment of their performance is still ongoing, but already some of them are in line with what is required to produce efficient devices for waste heat harvesting.

If you are interested in the project, check out its website www.START-HEproject.com, and find out more; you can follow also on Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, etc. Subscribing to the mailing list on the website will allow to directly receive news about the project, and in particular the newsletter.

Figure 11: EPMA Newsletter #129, November 2023, page 10.

5.3 SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media are used to engage the audience, bring them to the website, and in general to disseminate and communicate (also to the wider public) about START activities, results and partners.

The project's social media accounts have been already created and reported in deliverable D6.1 ("Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools"), submitted on 29th July 2022. The social media activated are:

- Twitter/X (partner responsible: LPRC): https://twitter.com/START_HEproject
- LinkedIn (EPMA): <https://www.linkedin.com/company/86266991/>
- YouTube (EPMA): <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCHVjEhpVz9uaEgzlCj2InPA>
- Twitch (LPRC): https://www.twitch.tv/start_he_project
- SlideShare (ASGMI): <https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/>

In addition to these, an account on the Zenodo service⁹, the Open Data service created by CERN within the OpenAIRE project in 2013, that also offers the creation of a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) number, has been created (see for instance the document [Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling | Zenodo](#)) by LNEG and is used, in parallel with SlideShare, to help us assuring that the rule for OpenAccess publication is fulfilled (see chapter 6.4), together with the publication on our website and social media.

5.3.1 Activity on Twitter/X

START Twitter/X posts have two main goals:

1. sharing information with the community on the project's goals, objectives, and concept, as well as on the relevant communication activities such as presentations at conferences, the START video, the webinars, workshops and meetings, and online materials and,
2. sharing how the START project contributes to the main topics of interest, e.g., thermoelectrics, reuse of mining waste, waste heat energy, green energy and sustainability.

During M13-M18 a total of 32 posts were made, spanning from 01/06/2023 to 23/11/2023, and contributing to the following statistics:

- 1) Total number of Followers: 147 (raising from 70 since last 6 months)
- 2) Number of views/Impressions during the period: 10017

Total number of Audience (counted as Engagements + Detail Expands + New followers + Profile visits) statistics are somewhat similar to the previous period regarding the number of posts and expected Impressions and Engagements. Where the numbers are better than expected is in the number of page followers, which raised from 70 to 147 within 6 months. This is still a somewhat low number of followers, but the statistics of Impressions and Engagements make up for it, indicating that the impact of the publications on Twitter/X is remarkable.

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/>

Figure 12 shows the “homepage” of the START Twitter/X account. See also paragraph 5.7.1.2 for relevant KPIs.

Figure 12: The START Twitter profile (status on 11/11/2023).

5.3.2 Activity on LinkedIn

The activity on LinkedIn continued along the two already established main lines:

- Achieving a larger audience for the START page. This was done mainly by EPMA, using the network available to them. At the date of writing D6.3 (29 November 2022), the page followers were 142, on 6th May 2023 the number increased to 312, and on 9th November 2023 followers are now 408 (Figure 13).
- Posting project news to bring interest and send interested people to the website, if possible, to let them subscribe to the project’s mailing list.

Occasionally, some third-party news (e.g., a post on the Critical Raw Materials Act) have been published, in order to create some traffic to the page (a similar approach has been followed on Twitter).

Followers have been growing steadily, growing to more than 300 in May 2023. It is believed that this number will further increase. The objective is to reach 800 followers by the end of the project, and, although difficult to attain, we hope that especially when scientific results will be shown, it will be easier to attract followers.

Figure 13: LinkedIn START followers since beginning of November 2022 and until beginning of November 2023 (no “sponsored” followers are present, only “organic”, i.e., not “purchased”).

Concerning posts, in the period between 09/05/2022 and 09/11/2023¹⁰ there were:

- 23 posts on the START page (almost 1 per week).
- 5 posts on LinkedIn groups (“EPMA networking group”, “Sustainability professionals” group, “Thermoelectrics” group, “Thermoelectric matters” group, “Metallurgy and Materials Science” group).
- posts on personal accounts (surely more than 17, as this is the number posted by B. Vicenzi, the EPMA main contributor to LinkedIn, on his own account, that lists almost 1800 followers and about 1600 connections) by members of the consortium, that have been only partly considered in the evaluation of impact.

See also paragraph 5.7.1.1 for relevant KPIs.

5.3.3 Activity on YouTube

On YouTube the activity is lower, as it practically involves the uploading of the videos produced during the project. There are now 11 videos on the START YouTube channel, for a total of more than 5 h of video time, ranging from just above 1 m to 1 h 17 m each. Here follows an update of the data about views. All data reported here have been acquired on 9th November 2023.

¹⁰ The previous deliverable D6.4 reported data until 8th May 2023.

5.3.3.1 START introductory video (published on 25th October 2022)

To date, visualisations on YouTube have grown to 115, with a slow growth that is still continuing after more than one year, at a more or less constant rate.

Figure 14: Statistics for visualisations of the START introductory video on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication).

The analysis of visualisation behaviour shows that 29% of the users viewed the video beyond the 30s mark, whereas the average duration of the views is 26 seconds.

Figure 15: Statistics for retention of viewers during the START introductory video (YouTube).

5.3.3.2 START Webinar #01 - 2023-28-02 (published on 6th March 2023)

After the initial week from publication, that obtained about 20 views, the views have grown to 39.

Figure 16: Statistics for visualisations of the START Webinar#01 on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication).

The video is longer than 1 hour, so retention is not very high, only 7.7% of the video is normally watched, for an average duration of 4m55s.

Figure 17: Statistics for retention of viewers during the START Webinar#01 video on YouTube.

5.3.3.3 START - 8th March 2023 - Gracia Olivenza (ASGMI) (published on 8th March 2023)

This was a short video that only got 5 visualisations on YouTube (but much more on other social media). So, no significant statistics in this case.

5.3.3.4 START - 8th March 2023 - Concepción Fernández Leyva (IGME-CSIC) (published on 8th March 2023)

This was a short video that only got 4 visualisations on YouTube (but much more on other social media). So, no significant statistics in this case.

5.3.3.5 START Webinar #02 - 2023-04-26 (published on 2nd May 2023)

This video was published only on 2nd May 2023, so a few visualisations (10) were already there in the report of D6.4. The visualisations at this point are 24. The average view duration is 42 s, and the average percentage viewed is 0.9%.

Figure 18 Statistics for visualisations of the START Webinar#02 on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication).

Figure 19: Statistics for retention of viewers during the START Webinar#02 video on YouTube.

5.3.3.1 START Webinar #03, D. Crane presentation - 2023-05-31 (published on 12th July 2023)

This video, that includes only the presentation by D. Crane during the third webinar held in a hybrid format on 21st May 2023, was published on 12th July 2023. The views at this point are 59. The average view duration is 2m10 s, and the average percentage viewed is 4.7%.

Figure 20: Statistics for visualisations of the presentation by D. Crane in the START Webinar#03 on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication)

Figure 21: Statistics for retention of viewers during the presentation by D. Crane in the START Webinar#03 video on YouTube.

5.3.3.2 START Webinar #03, J. Hollis presentation - 2023-05-31 (published on 14th July 2023)

This video, that includes only the presentation by J. Hollis during the third webinar held in a hybrid format on 21st May 2023, was published on 14th July 2023. The views at this point are 11. The average view duration is 39 s, and the average percentage viewed is 2.7%.

Figure 22: Statistics for visualisations of the presentation by J. Hollis in the START Webinar#03 on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication)

Figure 23: Statistics for retention of viewers during the presentation by J. Hollis in the START Webinar#03 video on YouTube.

5.3.3.3 START Webinar #03, START partners presentations - 2023-05-31 (published on 17th July 2023)

This video, that includes only the presentation by START partners during the third webinar held in a hybrid format on 21st May 2023, was published on 17th July 2023. The views at this point are 22. The average view duration is 3m 13 s, and the average percentage viewed is 7.0%.

Figure 24: Statistics for visualisations of the presentation by various START partners in the START Webinar#03 on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication)

Figure 25: Statistics for retention of viewers during the presentation by various START partners in the START Webinar#03 video on YouTube.

5.3.3.4 START LCA Workshop - 2023-06-23 (published on 21st July 2023)

This video, that includes only the public part of the workshop, with the generalities on LCA, and is an activity of WP5, was published on 21st July 2023. The visualisations at this point are 21. The average view duration is 40 s, and the average percentage viewed is 1.5%.

Another video with the full footage has not been disclosed, because it contains the second part of the workshop that is confidential for the consortium partners.

Figure 26: Statistics for visualisations of the LCA Workshop on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication)

Figure 27: Statistics for retention of viewers of the LCA Workshop video on YouTube.

5.3.3.5 Starty #2 video (published on 18th October 2023)

This video was created separating the cartoon from the 2nd issue of the Starty series into slides, to be used as a rolling video in events. It was also uploaded to YouTube, but not advertised, so only 4 views are present at the moment.

A similar video will be prepared from Starty #3.

5.3.4 Activity on Twitch

Twitch has not been used yet.

5.3.5 Activity on SlideShare

As already reported in the previous deliverables D6.3 and D6.4, SlideShare had been used to host documents prepared that were also uploaded to the website, and some on Zenodo. In the following Table 2 the views collected on SlideShare are shown for each item.

Table 2: Presentations and documents uploaded to Slideshare in previous periods and their performance. In parenthesis, the change from the previous deliverable D6.4, i.e., the status in May 2023).

PRESENTATION/ DOCUMENT	LINK	PERFORMANCE
"Green energy harvesting – State of the art"	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/green-energy-harvesting	44 views (+21)
"Project START: From WASTE to HIGH-TECH", presentation at EU-Latin America Raw Materials Convention 2022 (Santiago de Chile, 3-4 November 2022) given by Daniel de Oliveira (LNEG).	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/project-start-from-waste-to-hightech	15 views (+3)
Presentation at World PM 2022 (Lyon, 9-13 October 2022) given by Filipe Neves (LNEG).	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/presentations-at-world-pm2022	10 views (+2)
START Factsheet in Portuguese.	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/sistemas-sustentveis-de-captura-de-energia-baseados- numa-abordagem-inovadora-de-reciclagem-de-resduos-de-mina	5 views (+0)
START Factsheet in English.	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/sustainable-energy-harvesting-systems-based-on-innovative-mine-waste-recycling	5 views (+1)
START Flyer.	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/start-flyer-254343547	6 views (+0)
START Newsletter Issue #1	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/startnewsletterissue1pdf	17 views (+8)
Starty Explains START – The comics (multilingual)	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/startyexplainsstartpdf	5 views (+1)
START Newsletter Issue #2	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/startnewsletterissue2pdf	16 views (+16, uploaded 28/05/2023)

In the last period, only a few more documents were added to SlideShare (Table 3).

Table 3: Presentations and documents uploaded to Slideshare in the last period and their performance.

PRESENTATION/ DOCUMENT	LINK	PERFORMANCE
Powder Metallurgy Review, Spring 2023	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/powder-metallurgy-review-spring-2023	1 view (uploaded on 13th November 2023)
START Supercluster Event Abstract	https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/startsupercluster2023finalpdf	0 views (uploaded on 16/11/2023)
START Newsletter Issue #3	https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/start-newsletter-3	0 views (uploaded 29/11/2023)

5.4 START NEWSLETTER

The project's Newsletter is published on its website and social media every 6 months, starting from Issue 1 at M06, November 2022. The name was decided among the consortium to be "RECOVER – REFORM - REUSE": this was made to give more appeal to the newsletter. The consortium chose a name that is suggesting that the content will not be just related to START but will be connected with the sustainability solutions imagined, the ideas of recovering (mine wastes, heat), of transformation (of wastes into raw materials for thermoelectric devices, of otherwise dispersed heat into electrical energy), and of reusing (materials and energy achieved to obtain better efficiency).

The information conveyed in the various issues of the newsletter will in fact always include general information about START, thermoelectric materials, energy harvesting from waste heat, and linked sustainability topics, including state-of-the-art documents and scientific reviews, updates on project activities, project events and other dissemination topics, with invitation to join events where START will be featured, the description of consortium partners (typically 2 per issue), and all information on the various ways to keep informed about START (links to website, social media, link to the contact and subscription forms, etc.).

Being completely public, the information in the Newsletter must be duly checked in order to avoid IPR management issues. The direct distribution is partly based on a list of subscribers (and partly on social media and other partners networks). To create this list, the website tool for registration is used, and social media posts attract new subscribers to the website tool.

Here we update the distribution data for the first two issues, and give some info on issue #3, that was published just before this deliverable.

The KPI foreseen for the newsletter is the distribution to at least 500 recipients for each issue.

5.4.1 Newsletter issue #1

Issue #1 was published on 28th November 2022 (and covered in deliverable D6.3). It consists of 11 pages.

From the website, the newsletter has been downloaded 331 times, a strong increase from the figure of 193 (6th May 2023). It is likely that some more downloads will happen when subsequent issues are published.

On LinkedIn this issue obtained more than 400 impressions, with about 100 clicks and a high engagement rate. Twitter gave almost 900 impressions in the first year. On Zenodo¹¹ it was uploaded on 29th November 2022 and was viewed 30 times and downloaded 33 times (data of 9th November 2023).

In D6.3 we already documented that it had been delivered to more than 500 recipients; with time, downloads are now above 350 (counting also clicks on Twitter and LinkedIn, the 500 mark could have been passed), and still increasing after 1 year.

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/7377126>

5.4.2 Newsletter issue #2

The Issue 2 of the newsletter was first published on 22nd May 2023 (see D6.4) and had more than double pages compared to #1 (23 compared to 11).

In D6.4 we already documented that it had been delivered to more than 500 recipients.

From the website, the newsletter has been downloaded 204 times, a better figure than Issue #1 after 6 months. Again, it is likely that some more downloads will happen when subsequent issues are published.

On LinkedIn this issue obtained about 250 impressions to date. Twitter reports about 460 impressions. On Zenodo¹² it was uploaded on 25th May 2023 and was viewed 29 times and downloaded 20 times (data of 9th November 2023).

Thus, downloads are now about 220, plus some clicks on Twitter and LinkedIn.

5.4.3 Newsletter issue #3

The Issue 3 of the newsletter was first published on 29th November 2023. It consists of 25 pages (Issue #1 had 11 pages and Issue #2 had 23 pages). Using the same template previously used, text and images were collected from the different partners and were graphically rearranged to generate this issue. The content (a full version is available in Annex I) is as follows:

- Editorial from the Coordinator F. Neves
- STARTY – 3: Tetrahedrite – The material
- The effort for STARTY in many languages
- START Chronicles: Geology, thermoelectrics and more
 - News from Work Package 2 “Selection of mine waste sites; physical mineral separation and concentration: relevant mine waste sites in Germany”
 - News from the labs (Work Packages 3, 4, 5)
 - START first annual meeting in Madrid
 - START webinar #3
 - START internal LCA Workshop
 - START lectured at the 21st EPMA Summer School in Dresden, 21st July 2023
 - START lectured at the 2nd Edition of Summer School “Materials For Energy Transition” in Porto, 7th September 2023
 - START other dissemination events
- Technical pills
 - Designing optimal thermoelectric sulphides
 - Powder metallurgy of tetrahedrites
- Meet the Scientific Advisory Board Members (Jean-Yves Escabasse)
- Consortium tour
 - ASGMI
 - GeniCore
- Contacts

¹² <https://zenodo.org/records/7925963>

The structure is similar to that of Issue #2, and we continued the introduction to the members of the Scientific Advisory Board with an interview to Jean-Yves Escabasse, and the introduction to consortium members with ASGMI and GeniCore.

The newsletter was uploaded to the website on the Documents page (with reference also in the News page) on 29th November 2023 and was uploaded also to Zenodo¹³ and SlideShare¹⁴ the same day. It was advertised on Twitter (30th November 2023) and LinkedIn (29th November 2023). A mailing to the START mailing list was carried out on 30th November 2023. A mailing to the START mailing list was made on 30th November 2023. The launch of Issue #3 will also be announced on the EPMA weekly Newsletter for members in the first week of December 2023 and later to non-members (about 1600 and 400 contacts, respectively). A news item on the EPMA quarterly newsletter will be sent to all EPMA members (about 1600 contacts) in 2024. The data for downloads will be analysed in the next weeks.

5.5 START COMICS - STARTY

As already explained in previous Deliverables, START is making use of a comics character, “Starty, the robot”, that will be employed as much as possible to make communication more appealing also to those categories in the target that are not too scientifically involved in the subject, including the general public. This character will guide the reader or viewer into the START contents. Starty already was the main character in the introductory video developed in September 2022, in the first issue of the START Newsletter “RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE” issued in November 2022, and in the second issue of May 2023.

This strip of Newsletter #1, where our testimonial gave basic info about START, was later translated in 11 more languages: 10 spoken in the consortium, plus Turkish, published with the title “Starty explains START (multilingual edition)” on the website and on Zenodo, in March/April 2023. Since then, it has been downloaded 39 times from Zenodo and 215 times from the website.

In Newsletter Issue #2, Starty’s space was 3 pages, and the same translation exercise was carried out, this time for 13 languages (11 from the consortium, plus Turkish and Catalan). The “booklet” of 41 pages with all versions was published on the website on 30th August 2023 and was downloaded 101 times from there (data of 9th November 2023). On Zenodo, it was posted on 29th August 2023, and downloaded 110 times. An excerpt (the version in Catalan) is visible in Figure 28.

¹³ 10.5281/zenodo.10184764

¹⁴ <https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/start-newsletter-3>

Figure 28: Starty multilingual issue #2, excerpt with the Catalan version.

In the Newsletter Issue #3, Starty’s comic story is 4 pages long (see Annex 1). It will be translated in the next months, probably in 14 languages (Hungarian is planned).

Starty has also been used again for videos (see chapter 5.6).

5.6 VIDEOS

According to what was planned in the proposal, at least 5 videos will be produced during the project:

- 2 short videos (0.5-1 min), one at the start of the project to raise awareness and one at the end to summarise results. The language should be suitable for a wider audience; animations or cartoons could be used to attract non-specialists. One video at M04 (September 2022), one at M48 (May 2026).
- 2 longer videos (but still not too long, max 3 min) during the project, focusing on project topics and activities. The target should be more to groups 2-3, i.e., scientists, engineers, and entrepreneurs. Both videos are due at M48 (May 2026)
- 1 detailed video (about 5 min) at mid project (M24, May 2024), highlighting the results of the first part of the project.

Other videos could be produced, like:

- Interviews with key partners, describing the project or specific topics
- Recording of presentations given in events
- Short ads for specific events or for the “serious game”

EPMA normally is the partner taking care of producing the videos but will ask all relevant partners to help by delivering videos, images, and text. The videos are hosted on YouTube and/or Twitch, embedded in the START website, and posted on other social media like LinkedIn and Twitter.

The KPIs decided for these tools are basically views. A minimum of 100 views per video is the base KPI, and an overall average above 200 views/video is an additional KPI. Social media analysis tools allow collecting even further information about the audience.

5.6.1 START introductory video

A short introductory video for the project has been created in September 2022. In it, Starty gives the introductory info about START. The video was uploaded to the START YouTube channel, embedded in the START website (home page and Multimedia page), and posted to LinkedIn and Twitter. The video has been used in many dissemination events, starting with World PM2022 and Raw Materials Week 2022.

This is the situation of views on YouTube on 9th November 2023:

- YouTube (published on 25th October 2022):
 - views: 115
 - Average duration of viewing: 0m26s
 - Average view rate, %: 29%

As documented in the previous deliverable D6.4, LinkedIn¹⁵ gave about 800 additional views, while Twitter contributed with 60 more impressions with the first post; about 30 more with subsequent posts.

¹⁵ LinkedIn data are available until 1 year after the publication, after that the posts are not retrievable anymore.

The number of views, especially from LinkedIn, largely exceeds the minimum set, and is also way above the average requested of 200.

5.6.2 Other videos uploaded in earlier periods

5.6.2.1 Presentation of START at the Science Week 2022, Madrid

Video not produced by the project, but recorded by the event organisers, and made available (it is in Spanish): 194 views on YouTube at the moment.

5.6.2.2 8th March videos

Self-recorded by the two female members of the START team on the occasion of the International Women Day. On the website's News page, 12 visualisations. On YouTube, a total of 9 views. On LinkedIn page, 148 and 151 video views. On Twitter, 96 impressions and 13 total engagements.

5.6.2.3 Webinar #01

Footage of the first START webinar, held on 28th February 2023 (1 h 3 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 39. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 174 (+115 on a private account) and 309 views, respectively. It might still be posted as a video directly, to collect more views.

5.6.2.4 Webinar #02

Footage of the second START webinar, held on 26th April 2023 (1 h 17 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 24. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 133 (+139 on a private account) and 558 views, respectively. It might still be posted as a video directly, to collect more views.

5.6.3 Other videos uploaded in the last 6 months

5.6.3.1 Webinar #03 - Crane

Footage of the first presentation in the third START webinar, held on 31st May 2023 (47 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 59. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 317 (+303 on a private account) and 81 views, respectively. It might still be posted as a video directly, to collect more views.

5.6.3.2 Webinar #03 - Hollis

Footage of the second presentation in the third START webinar, held on 31st May 2023 (24.5 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 11. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 363 (+149 on a private account) and 173 views, respectively. It might still be posted as a video directly, to collect more views.

5.6.3.3 Webinar #03 – Consortium partners

Footage of the other presentations in the third START webinar, held on 31st May 2023 (46 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 20. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 148 (+218 on a private account) and 1304 views, respectively. It might still be posted as a video directly, to collect more views.

5.6.3.4 *LCA workshop*

Footage of the START workshop webinar, held on 23rd June 2023 (45 m). On YouTube, the number of views is 21. On LinkedIn and Twitter/X the posts collected 235 (+307 on a private account) and 102 views, respectively. It might still be posted as a video directly, to collect more views.

5.7 CONTINUOUS EVALUATION OF D&C PERFORMANCE

5.7.1 KPIs

KPIs are “a quantifiable measure of performance over time for a specific objective”. Although they are not the same as metrics, in the case of measuring the performance of a website or a social media that is normal.

To assess the dissemination, START will collect metrics from the website, and the social media, and will compare some selected KPIs to chosen reference values that the project expects to meet of the years. A list of the KPIs imagined, with their reference values, is given in Table 4.

Table 4: KPIs considered for D&C activities.

Tool	KPI	Reference value
Project website	Visitors	Year 1: 2000 Year 4: 4000
Twitter	Followers	Year 1: 1000 End: 2500
LinkedIn	Followers	End:800
Videos	Views	More than 100/video Average 200
Newsletters	Addressees	More than 500/issue
Webinars/ seminars/ workshop	Audience	100
Serious online game	Visitors	300
Other publications	Reach	More than 400000

According to previous project experiences, as already shown in deliverable D6.1 (“Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools”), an Excel file, named Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination (MTOD) is used to collect the data of dissemination performance on social media, in order to quantify the audience reached and the interest raised.

This is located on the START SharePoint (its address is [START/Work Packages/WP6 - Dissemination and communication/START Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination.xlsx](#)¹⁶) and contains all the details collected from the different social media posts and contents, and from the website. A view of the present status of the file is visible in the screenshot of Figure 29.

The file allows to calculate total audience and views of the actions, and the ratio between views and audience for each action. In this way, during the project course, priorities about the social media could be given.

The data from MTOD is used to update the Funding & Tender website page on Dissemination (see 5.7.3). At present, about 240 lines are included in the file; the sum of all audience data is about 520k and the sum of views is more than 56k. Views have had highs of about 1850 (on Twitter) and

¹⁶ Note: this is a private address, not accessible from outside the Consortium.

1400 (on LinkedIn), with a median of about 170 and an average of about 239 (slightly increasing from the previous data).

We believe that, considering the initial phase and the fact that this is a new subject for many of the contacts, the performance can be considered satisfactory: views have a remarkable median and average, so many of the followers actually visualise our content.

5.7.1.1 LinkedIn

For LinkedIn, the number of followers is now above 408 (see also chapter 5.3.2), that is still below the target of 800 followers at the end of the project, but in line with the possibility of reaching the KPI at the end of the project. A plot of the number of new followers (see Figure 30) shows some correlation with the newsletters and the webinars. Also, page views (Figure 31) had a peak at that time, and then lower numbers. Impressions (Figure 32) show a second peak around end of February 2023, presumably due to the first webinar.

Figure 30: LinkedIn Follower metrics (last 365 days).

Visitor highlights ?

966
Page views

447
Unique visitors

23
Custom button clicks

Visitor metrics ?

Page views ▼ All pages ▼ | All filters

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Desktop	603
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mobile	363

Figure 31: LinkedIn Page views metrics (last 365 days).

Figure 32: LinkedIn Impressions metrics (last 365 days).

5.7.1.2 Twitter – now X

For Twitter/X the number of actual followers (currently at 147) is somewhat low, still compared to the planned target for Year 1 (1000 followers). This can be explained by the relative lack of project news and activities, which are planned to expand from year 2 onwards, and also by the turmoil regarding Twitter itself as a platform (acquisition of Twitter – including the “political” debate about the new owner -, transformation into X, monetisation of the platform). The number of audiences reached – counting the number of views/impressions, Likes, Retweets, Engagements, Detail Expands, New followers and Profile visits – is, however, interesting (reaching above 10000 between June 2023 and November 2023): this number corresponds to real engagement with the project posts, so it can be considered as a more reliable parameter for KPIs assessment. There was an interesting raise in the number of followers, coupled with a standard number of posts published and Impressions and Engagements obtained.

The first two figures below (Figure 33, Figure 34) show the START Twitter activity for the period covered by this Deliverable. The last figure (Figure 35) shows, specifically, the increase of the START Twitter/X activity in July 2023, coinciding with a period of posting regarding the 3rd webinar, the LCA webinar, the work within WP2 and the outcomes and benefits of START for powder metallurgy stakeholders. This was the period with most impressions and engagements.

Your Tweets earned **7.7K impressions** over this **91 day period**

Figure 33: Twitter impressions and Tweets from 01/06/23 to 30/08/2023

Your Tweets earned **3.3K impressions** over this **73 day period**

Figure 34: Twitter impressions and Tweets from 31/08/23 to 11/11/2023.

Your Tweets earned **4.2K impressions** over this **31 day period**

Figure 35: Twitter impressions and Tweets in July 2023.

It must be noted that in addition to these posts, on Twitter, and now on X, LPRC has in many cases reposted news from other accounts, concerning raw materials, sustainability, thermoelectrics, waste heat recovery, etc. This helped in growing the follower base and kept the account busy between project posts. We have not counted these views and impressions, but they surely contribute to the visibility of the account.

5.7.1.3 Videos

The KPIs for video are: at least 100 views each, and average of 200 views. As we are producing a large number of videos compared to the original number of 5, it would be really difficult to maintain this as a general rule. We will apply only to the 5 “institutional” videos. Only the first one has been prepared until now, the introductory video. It exceeds the KPI, considering all views on all platforms and not only on YouTube.

- Introductory video:

- YouTube: 115 views
- LinkedIn: about 800 in the first year
- Twitter about 60 in the first year (so the total amount on social media is about 860 views).

So, the KPI of at least 100 views, and even the average expected of 200 views, are exceeded by far.

For the other videos, we have collected now more than 180 views on YouTube and many more on LinkedIn, both when the videos have been posted directly (e.g., about 300 for the International Women Day videos) and definitely much more as views of the posts.

For the webinar footage videos we feel that the length makes them not so appealing, only a few viewers have watched the whole events apart from those who were present live. For this reason, the third webinar has been split in three shorter videos, and this paid off: the 3 videos from Webinar #3 collected a total of 90 views on YouTube, compared to 39 and 24 for the first two long footage videos from the other webinars.

5.7.1.4 Project website

Concerning the project website, we remind here that the analysis is limited to the data after 17th October 2022 because of an erroneous setting of Google Analytics: all data before 17th October have been lost. In addition to that, the Google Analytics services have changed on 5th July 2023, so more or less 1 month into the period covered by this deliverable, and comparison or aggregation of data with the previous period is now difficult. For all the available periods, these data have been collected:

- Audience (users, new users, numbers of sessions per user, pageviews, pages/session)
- Acquisition
- Behaviour (visited pages)

For the reason written above, in the following pages we switch to the new data available for the website (from 5th July 2023 until the first part of November 2023, so on the base of 132 days), and we will compare what is possible with the previous data.

A chart of the activity on pages in 2023 is shown in Figure 36. Data are obtained from the new Google Analytics service, so they start, as mentioned, on 05/07/2023. As in previous periods some suspicious peaks of traffic were visible, we have checked the peak on 16th October 2023, and by looking at country/device/referral data we concluded that the peak is not due to bots (and not to particular activities of advertisement by the consortium) but for some reason to “normal” traffic.

This means that, compared to last data, there was no need to estimate the effect of spurious data in boosting the performance, all data can be considered as genuinely related to rightful traffic.

Views by Page path and screen class over time

Figure 36: Page Views in 2023 for the new Google Analytics channel for the project website: data start from 05/07/2023. The peak on 16th October is not linked to particular activities nor due to “bots”.

Figure 37 is the most comprehensive table, as it shows the Audience data for this last period, including Views, Users, and Sessions.

The most visited page is still the home page, and all 7 main pages are in the most visited 8 pages. The only news items that are in the first 10 are those on the LCA workshop, the Annual Meeting in Madrid and the multilingual Starty booklet. The total views of about 1800 would scale on a yearly basis to above 5000, that is, already above the KPI of 4000/yr that is due at the end of the project. We believe that this figure will increase when the information will be including more project results and application-related breakthroughs. For comparison, the estimate from first year was in the range of 3600 (after subtracting the “bot effect”). This shows a clear growth.

Per user, the most viewed page is the News page.

Users were about 1160 (3200/yr) compared to 2400 for the first period (4200/yr), so this is some contraction, but clearly users view more pages compared to the first period.

Sessions are estimated to be about 4350/yr (1570 in this period). The duration of a session is on average close to 90 seconds, ranging from about 2 seconds to almost 10 minutes. Among the main pages, that with the highest average is the Documents page.

Pages-Users-Sessions							
Period:	05/07/2023	13/11/2023				Days:	132
Page	Views	Users	Views per user	Average engagement time	Sessions	Views per session	Average session duration
Total/365 days	5054.7	3218.6			4341.3		
Total/average	1828	1164	1.57	25.50	1570	1.16	85.96
/	927	616	1.50	20.55	801	1.16	77.80
/the-project/	175	112	1.56	28.75	140	1.25	52.90
/documents/	163	88	1.85	28.70	133	1.23	165.46
/multimedia/	113	53	2.13	27.02	89	1.27	99.87
/news/	112	50	2.24	47.30	86	1.30	47.30
/consortium/	110	66	1.67	46.68	107	1.03	100.72
/watch-the-lecture-by-3drivers-on-use-of-lca-for-environmental-impact-assessment/	46	28	1.64	16.75	43	1.07	66.11
/contact/	42	35	1.20	13.60	39	1.08	139.84
/starts-1st-annual-meeting-successfully-run-in-madrid/	37	33	1.12	17.18	35	1.06	46.24
/starty-is-back-in-13-languages/	25	20	1.25	19.75	23	1.09	66.36
/start-webinar-3-watch-doug-cranes-speech-on-thermoelectric-energy-harvesting/	22	18	1.22	30.39	20	1.10	58.45
/start-webinar-3-start-partners-share-knowledge-about-tetrahydrites-in-europe/	14	9	1.56	31.22	12	1.17	95.56
/start-on-powder-metallurgy-review/	8	6	1.33	22.17	8	1.00	189.91
/start-webinar-3-watch-julie-hollis-speech-on-the-eus-crm-ambitions-ant-the-role-of-eurogeosurveys/	8	5	1.60	19.80	6	1.33	267.85
/starty-comics-starty-explains-start-now-available-in-12-languages/	5	5	1.00	12.80	5	1.00	156.09
/join-the-third-webinar-on-may-31st-live-from-our-project-meeting/	3	3	1.00	7.00	3	1.00	7.14
/recover-reform-reuse-issue-1-our-start-newsletter-is-here/	3	3	1.00	11.67	3	1.00	11.94
/the-project-scientific-advisory-board-has-been-appointed/	3	2	1.50	11.50	3	1.00	83.09
/*	2	2	1.00	25.00	2	1.00	21.75
/more-than-60-participants-in-starts-first-free-webinar/	2	2	1.00	13.50	2	1.00	16.51
/news-we-started/	2	2	1.00	42.00	2	1.00	538.38
/recover-reform-reuse-issue-2-is-now-available-may-2023/	2	2	1.00	7.50	2	1.00	98.49
/iwd2023/	1	1	1.00	76.00	1	1.00	76.52
/start-free-webinar-series-connect-to-our-research/	1	1	1.00	0.00	2.00	0.50	2.75
/start-looks-southwest-the-second-start-webinar-connects-to-latin-america/	1	1	1.00	0.00	2.00	0.50	2.68
/the-footage-of-the-second-start-free-webinar-dedicated-to-latin-america-is-now-available/	1	1	1.00	51.00	1.00	1.00	82.21

Figure 37: Views, Users and Sessions data for the project website (05/07/2023 to 13/11/2023) and projections to 1 yr data.

The distribution by countries (Figure 38) shows an interesting engagement from the Netherlands, followed by USA and Portugal. Please note also engagement from China (more views but not so engaged), Japan and India. Visibility is clearly extended to the whole world.

Country	05/07/2023	13/11/2023				Days: 132
Country	Users	New users	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate	Engaged sessions per user	Average engagement time
Netherlands	81	80	78	0.60	0.96	45.63
United States	67	67	15	0.22	0.22	12.79
Portugal	64	64	78	0.59	1.22	78.56
Finland	62	62	16	0.25	0.26	9.68
Austria	52	52	8	0.15	0.15	11.79
France	51	51	33	0.39	0.65	57.63
Spain	46	46	32	0.52	0.70	82.20
Germany	31	30	28	0.64	0.90	85.03
Poland	25	25	17	0.40	0.68	32.32
China	24	24	2	0.08	0.08	3.25
Japan	19	19	8	0.38	0.42	28.42
United Kingdom	18	18	15	0.60	0.83	61.56
Belgium	17	16	13	0.57	0.76	36.41
India	17	17	6	0.30	0.35	6.00
Italy	13	12	17	0.52	1.31	56.85
Norway	12	12	4	0.22	0.33	23.67
Brazil	6	6	3	0.50	0.50	7.17
Canada	5	5	3	0.60	0.60	22.20
Greece	5	5	5	1.00	1.00	121.40
South Korea	5	5	3	0.60	0.60	9.20
Denmark	4	4	3	0.75	0.75	125.50
Iran	4	4	4	0.80	1.00	31.25
Latvia	4	4	5	1.00	1.25	53.25
Morocco	4	4	1	0.17	0.25	4.50
Singapore	4	4	2	0.33	0.50	21.00
Switzerland	4	4	3	0.75	0.75	35.75
Taiwan	4	4	3	0.75	0.75	30.75
Colombia	3	3	1	0.33	0.33	3.33
Czechia	3	3	4	0.80	1.33	98.33
Ghana	3	3	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Sri Lanka	3	3	2	0.67	0.67	20.67
Turkiye	3	3	3	0.75	1.00	174.67
Uganda	3	3	2	0.67	0.67	11.00
Bangladesh	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	26.00
Chile	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	9.50
Ecuador	2	2	0	0.00	0.00	2.00
Hong Kong	2	2	1	0.33	0.50	4.00
Indonesia	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	3.00
Mexico	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	4.00
Nigeria	2	2	2	0.67	1.00	85.50
Russia	2	2	2	0.67	1.00	174.50
Ukraine	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	27.50
Uzbekistan	2	2	1	0.50	0.50	5.00
Australia	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Belarus	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	6.00
Burkina Faso	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	10.00
Cambodia	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Costa Rica	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	8.00
Croatia	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Cuba	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Cote d'Ivoire	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	2.00
Egypt	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	10.00
Ireland	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Israel	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	21.00
Jordan	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	60.00
Kazakhstan	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	15.00
Lithuania	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	2.00
Madagascar	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Malaysia	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Pakistan	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	24.00
Panama	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	8.00
Romania	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	25.00
Rwanda	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	77.00
Saudi Arabia	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Serbia	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	59.00
Slovenia	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	0.00
Sweden	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Thailand	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	5.00
Tunisia	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	5.00
Venezuela	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	2.00
Yemen	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	29.00

Figure 38: Users and Sessions by Country data for the project website (05/07/2023 to 13/11/2023).

Looking at the sources for connections to the website (Figure 39), most happen directly via typing in the address bar in the browser, followed by Google searches. LinkedIn is the 3rd contributor, then Sendinblue (the provider of our mailing service, so clicks on the mails that we deliver to our mailing list). Baidu (Chinese search engine) and Twitter (t.co) are also at the top of the list. Some other referrals are due to events where START is included in the useful links.

Sources						
Period:	05/07/2023	13/11/2023			Days:	132
Session source/medium	Users	Sessions	Engaged sessions	Average engagement time per session	Engaged sessions per user	Engagement rate
(direct) / (none)	404	538	233	29.34	0.58	0.43
google / organic	164	203	92	28.76	0.56	0.45
linkedin.com / referral	52	100	57	33.84	1.10	0.57
6fgo6.r.a.d.sendibm1.com / referral	29	31	11	26.74	0.38	0.35
baidu / organic	18	18	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
t.co / referral	11	12	4	18.42	0.36	0.33
bing / organic	6	7	5	74.71	0.83	0.71
lneg.pt / referral	6	12	6	48.58	1.00	0.50
macaronight.eu / referral	6	14	9	17.43	1.50	0.64
epma.com / referral	5	7	5	53.86	1.00	0.71
facebook.com / referral	5	5	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
reesilience.eu / referral	5	6	5	15.67	1.00	0.83
eis-he.eu / referral	3	6	5	13.83	1.67	0.83
(not set)	2	2	0	15.50	0.00	0.00
lnkd.in / referral	2	2	2	23.50	1.00	1.00
statics.teams.cdn.office.net / referral	2	4	1	36.75	0.50	0.25
lens.google.com / referral	1	1	1	24.00	1.00	1.00
mail.google.com / referral	1	2	1	35.50	1.00	0.50
mail.whut.edu.cn / referral	1	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
pl.linkedin.com / referral	1	1	1	75.00	1.00	1.00
youtube.com / referral	1	1	1	59.00	1.00	1.00
hypromag.com / referral	0	1	0	0.00	0.00	0.00

Figure 39: Users and Sessions by Sources and referrals data for the project website (05/07/2023 to 13/11/2023).

Compared to the past, mobile devices are increasing with respect to desktops as devices used for the connection (Figure 40).

Devices					
Period:	05/07/2023	13/11/2023		Days:	132
Device category	Users	New users	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate	Engaged sessions per user
desktop	532	531	376	0.49	0.71
mobile	174	174	62	0.32	0.36
tablet	5	5	1	0.17	0.20

Figure 40: Users and Sessions by Devices data for the project website (05/07/2023 to 13/11/2023).

Globally, we can consider the website performance as satisfactory, and the hope is that with the progress in the project, and more meaningful scientific content being published, the performance may become even better.

5.7.1.5 *Newsletter*

Concerning the newsletter, the distribution through the START mailing list now comprises about 170 names, more than double compared to the distribution list for Issue #1 (80). As mentioned elsewhere, EPMA has sent the link to download the various Newsletter issues to about 1600 EPMA member contacts via its weekly E-Mail Newsletter and in subsequent Newsletters to non-member contacts (about 400).

Thus, especially via the EPMA distribution, the target of 500 has been exceeded by far for all issues of the newsletter; clearly it must be correlated with the actual downloads recorded, but data for Issue #1 are also growing to above the 500 mark and this could happen with time for all subsequent issues.

5.7.2 *WP6 meetings*

To keep track of the activities and their performance, and steer them during the project, the WP6 main partners are called to meet, normally online but in-person meetings are also possible. These include:

- the WP6 leader (EPMA)
- the other WP6 task leader (ASGMI)
- the other partner responsible for social media accounts (LPRC)
- the coordinator (LNEG)
- the leaders of WPs, i.e., the components of the ExCom
- specific partners that will be invited if their participation will be useful in the discussion, for instance if their activity is required in the following months.

Anyway, during this semester, only smaller meetings were organised for specific discussions, like the detailed organisation of a particular event where only some partners are involved:

- 29 May 2023 Preparation of WP6 workshop in the Annual Meeting (EPMA-ASGMI) (online)

- 31 May 2023 START WP6 Workshop in the Annual Meeting (Madrid, all partners)
- 29 June 2023 Discussion on Continuous reporting and Zenodo (EPMA-LNEG) (online)
- 13 July 2023 Discussion on Ciaopeople collaboration with START (EPMA-LNEG-TEGnology-RGS-LPRC-ASGMI) (online)
- 29 September 2023 EPMA visit to LNEG (EPMA-LNEG)
- 6 October 2023 ERHASE-START meeting (EPMA-LNEG-ASGMI)
- 13 October 2023 Discussion on START participation at Supercluster Event Lapland (EPMA-LNEG-ASGMI)
- 18 October 2023 THERMOS - START meeting (EPMA-LNEG-ASGMI)
- 23 November 2023 Meeting on events and D&C activities in 2024 (EPMA-LNEG-LPRC-ASGMI-TEGnology)

The rest of the arrangement were discussed via E-Mail, bi- or multilaterally.

5.7.3 Continuous reporting on Funding&Tender website

The WP Leader (EPMA) is responsible of regularly updating the information on Dissemination and Communication in the relevant section in the project's Continuous Reporting on the Funding&Tender website. There are three pages dedicated to these topics on the portal: "Publications", "Dissemination" and "Communication".

At the latest, an update must be made before the end of each reporting period, as at each periodic report, all the information present in the Continuous Reporting section is automatically compiled to create Part A of the Periodic Technical Report. This was done in August 2023 (M15). The Publications page (Figure 41) contains many publications (actually some of them are doubles, we will clean this after making certain that all unique info is not lost). The "Communication" (Figure 42) and the "Dissemination" page (Figure 43) are also updated. Concerning these pages, it was not easy to comply with the rigid structure of the tables, that sometimes requires, for instance, that each activity described has to be directed to a single target group. This is clearly not the case with most of the activities we have carried out, and we suggest that a more flexible classification be adopted in the portal tables for the future.

#002n7v4 (EXTERNAL)

Grant Management
Project Continuous Report

101058632 (START) HORIZON-IA
Project Summary
Researchers involved in the project
Deliverables
Milestones
Critical Risks
Publications
Results
Dissemination activities
Communication Activities
Standards
Intellectual property rights (IPR)
Datasets
Impact
Impact Continuation
Other Results

Publications SAVE

Suggested publications from OpenAIRE (5 pending publications and 0 discarded publications)

	Type	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal or equivalent	Month and Year of publication	PID (Publisher version of record)	PID of the deposited publication	Actions
1	Other	Creation of the project website, graphical identit						
2	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Presentation of the START project at the World Pa	Neves, F.	ZENODO				
3	Publication in Conference proceedings/Workshop	Presentation of the START project at the 2022 EU-	de Oliveira, Daniel	ZENODO				
4	Article in Journal	GREEN ENERGY HARVESTING - STATE OF THE ART	START Project		26-07-2022			
5	Article in Journal	Presentation of the START project at the 2022 EU-	de Oliveira, Daniel		04-11-2022			

Project publications (13 publications)

	Type	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal or equivalent	Number	Peer-reviewed	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	PID (publisher version of record)	PID of deposited publication	Actions
1	Article in Journal	The START project: Creating a sustain	Filipe Neves; Bruno Vicenzi; Alvisé Bia	Powder Metallurgy Review magazine: :		False	False	10.5281/zenodo.7850149		
2	Publication in conference proceeding,	Presentation of the START project at t	de Oliveira, Daniel	ZENODO		False	False	10.5281/zenodo.7327406	10.5281/zenodo.7327407	
3	Publication in conference proceeding,	Presentation of the START project at t	Neves, F.	ZENODO		False	False			
4	Books/monographs	Starty explains START	START Project			False	True	10.5281/zenodo.7746440	10.5281/zenodo.7746441	
5	Other	COMO GENERAR ELECTRICIDAD A PART	Ester Bolxereu Vila; Concepción Fern			False	False	10.5281/zenodo.7417730		
6	Other	D6.1 - Creation of the project websit	START project			False	False	10.5281/zenodo.8270292		
7	Other	RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE - START News	START project			False	False	10.5281/zenodo.7377126		
8	Other	RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE - START News	START project			False	False	10.5281/zenodo.7925963		
9	Other	GREEN ENERGY HARVESTING - STATE OF	START Project			False	False	10.5281/zenodo.6906481	10.5281/zenodo.6906480	
10	Other	GREEN ENERGY HARVESTING - STATE OF	START project			False	False	10.5281/zenodo.6906480	10.5281/zenodo.6906481	

* 'open access' means the practice of providing online access to research outputs resulting from actions funded under the Programme, in particular scientific publications and research data, free of charge to the end-user

Figure 41: Screenshot of the page dedicated to Publications on the Funding&Tender portal (13/11/2023).

Grant Management
Project Continuous Report
#002:n74 (EXTERNAL) HOW TO

101058632 (START)	HORIZON-IA	Project Summary	Researchers involved in the project	Deliverables	Milestones	Critical Risks	Publications	Results	Disseminat... activities	Communic... Activities	Standards	Intellectual property rights (IPR)	Datasets	Impact	Impact Continuati...	Other Results
Call: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01 Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07		✔	⚠	i	i	✔	i	✔	✔	✔	✔	✔	✔	✔	✔	✔

Communications Activities SAVE

There are no communication activities for this project yet

Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

List the communication activities carried out in the context of the project. Use the same labels used in your DEC plan.

[Add Communication Activity](#)

Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience	How? Communication channel	Outcome	Status	Actions
Technical promotional material	Leaflets, posters and roller banners to be used in exhi	Industry, business partners	Exhibition	No specific KPI for this activity	Ongoing	✗
Communication by social media	All project details (approach, activities, results) comm	Citizens	Social media	Posts online: audience >500k contacts, 40k \	Ongoing	✗
RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE Issue 2	Project newsletter. Information about project activit	Citizens	Newsletter	Delivered to 1600 + 400 EPMA contacts, 220	Delivered	✗
Starty the Robot	Cartoon character developed by the consortium as pr	Citizens	Newsletter	Posts with Starty in 12 languages explaining	Ongoing	✗
Communication by project website	All project details (approach, activities, results) comm	Citizens	Website	>8000 page views until now (target KPI 2000	Ongoing	✗
RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE Issue 1	Project newsletter. Information about project activit	Citizens	Newsletter	Delivered to 1600 + 400 EPMA contacts, 400	Delivered	✗

[Validate](#)

Figure 42: Screenshot of the page dedicated to Communications on the Funding&Tender portal (13/11/2023).

#002:n74 (EXTERNAL)
Grant Management
Project Continuous Report

101058632 (START)	HORIZON-IA	Project Summary	Researchers involved in the project	Deliverables	Milestones	Critical Risks	Publications	Results	Dissemination activities	Communications Activities	Standards	Intellectual property rights (IPR)	Datasets	Impact	Impact Continuati...	Other Results
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Dissemination Activities SAVE

There is no dissemination activity for this project yet

▼ List the dissemination activities carried out in the context of the project. Include dissemination activities mentioned in the proposal and new ones.

[+ Add Dissemination Activity](#)

Dissemination Activity Name	What? Type of dissemination activity	Who? Target audience Reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Actions
EPMA Summer School START dissemination	Education and training events	Research communities, Industry, business partners	START lessons and experiences are given to participants in the EPMA	Ongoing	✗
Dissemination in scientific events	Conferences	Research communities, Industry, business partners, Innovators	START is taking part in many scientific events to disseminate its appr	Ongoing	✗
Clustering	Clustering activities	Research communities, Industry, business partners	Meetings are being carried out with many of the projects, initiatives	Ongoing	✗
Dissemination in Newsletter	Other	Other	In the Newsletter, START includes Technical Pills with technical inform	Ongoing	✗
START webinars	Education and training events	Research communities, Industry, business partners, Innovators	START organizes free webinars (3 to date) with presentations about t	Ongoing	✗

[Validate](#)

Figure 43: Screenshot of the page dedicated to Dissemination on the Funding&Tender portal (13/11/2023).

6 TASK 6.2: TECHNICAL AND SCIENTIFIC DISSEMINATION

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M01 to M48

All partners will submit papers in relevant conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and scientific journals to give information on the results of the START project.

- Relevant EPMA events (for the PM community mainly):
 - The EuroPM and/or WorldPM Congress and Exhibition series (a project booth is foreseen)
 - The EPMA technical seminars by sectors (Functional Materials, Hot Isostatic Pressing, etc.)
 - Sectoral Group meetings, e.g.:
 - European Functional Materials Sectoral Group (EuroFM)
 - European Hot Isostatic Pressing Sectoral Group (EuroHIP)
 - Environment, Health, Quality and Safety Working Group (EHQS).
- International Conference on Thermoelectrics (ICT/ECT/ACT conference series), and other conferences to be defined by the consortium.
- Special dissemination seminars and presentations (webinars or in person) on specific project-related topics:
 - contributions from the consortium
 - selected external speakers
 - ads on dedicated printed or online magazines (e.g., Journal of Degraded and Mining Lands Management, Journal of Environmental Management, Environmental Earth Sciences, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Mine Water and the Environment...)

External events to communicate to the public and to other scientific and industrial communities and improve the awareness of the energy and sustainability issues in the public: EPMA and other consortium partners will take part in

- At least 2 external events and exhibitions per year
- Possibly Science Festivals and Fairs (e.g., the European Researchers' Night) to communicate the scope of the project and improve the awareness of the energy and sustainability issues in the public.

Specific KPIs will be introduced to quantify the impact of project dissemination.

Publications and presentations in conferences, seminars and congresses are strongly encouraged: all consortium partners should try to organise a technical participation in an event to disseminate a part of the work carried out in START. This will broaden the audience for the project topics and in the end will create the condition for successful exploitation.

Thus, maybe with some exceptions, we expect that during the course of the project almost all partners will submit papers in relevant conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and scientific journals to give information on the results of the START project.

Addressing communities that are outside those already covered by the consortium members activities and by the standard journals, magazines and conferences/events is also rather important

for an innovative project like START. For this reason, the plan is to try addressing external communities by publishing well balanced papers and articles in more general magazines, or news services/websites (the Horizon Results, the Horizon Magazine, also suitable generic magazines, like for instance the Open Access Government magazine).

6.1 EVENTS LIST

In order to select the events where the partners, individually or as consortium, should take part, and take materials concerning the project, a “**START Events List**” is established and regularly updated by the WP6 leader (EPMA) on the START SharePoint and every partner will collaborate by giving information on possible events.

In this Excel file, the following information is collected for each event:

- Name of Event
- Priority: the partners are asked to evaluate what is the priority to give to this event in order to try maximising the impact by optimising the effort.
- Date of start of event
- Date of end of event
- Physical/Online/Hybrid: if available, information on the type of participation requested.
- Website: where possible, the link to obtain fresh info about the event
- Location: where the event will be held (in case, “online”)
- Type of audience: scientific (what sector), industrial (what sector), general (what composition) etc.
- START Booth: whether a START booth should be present at the event
- Partner Booth: whether a START partner booth should be present at the event (including name of partner)
- START lectures/papers: in case a presentation is given, details on the topic (e.g., “Generic project presentation” or a specific topic)
- START lecture/paper date: when the presentation will happen
- Presenter: who is going to present
- Reference partner: the partner who will be coordinating the participation
- Attendees: expected number of attendees

The list is the basis for discussion, in the meetings, about participation at the various events.

In Figure 44 the present status of the list is shown.

Event	Priority (1=high)	Date start	Date end	Physical /Online/ Hybrid	Website	Location	Type of audience	START Booth	Partner Booth	START lectures/papers	START lecture/paper date	Presenter	Reference partner	Attendees
1st START Webinar (LNEG)	1.00	28/02/2023	28/02/2023	Online	START website	-	All	-	-	Project pres	28/02/2023	F. Neves	LNEG	
1st START Webinar (LNEG)	1.00	28/02/2023	28/02/2023	Online	START website	-	Raw materials/mining	-	-	Technical pres	28/02/2023	D. Oliveira	LNEG	
GENERA 2023 (International Energy and Environment Fair)	2.00	21/02/2023	23/02/2023	Physical	https://www.ifema.es/en/genera	Madrid (Spain)	Energy and Environment							
PDAC 2023: The World's Premier Mineral Exploration & Mining Convention	1.00	05/03/2023	08/03/2023	Physical	https://www.pdac.ca/convention	Toronto (Canada)	Raw materials/mining						LNEG	
Sourcing the European energy transition from domestic resources - vision or wishful thinking?	1.00	25/04/2023	26/04/2023	Physical	https://www.greenpeg.eu/news.html	Uppsala, Sweden	Raw materials/mining						GEO	
2nd START Webinar (LNEG)	1	26/04/2023	26/04/2023	Online									LNEG	
EGU - European Geoscience Union (every year around April/May)	-	23/04/2023	28/04/2023	Physical	https://www.egu.eu/	Vienna (Austria)	Raw materials/mining							
EIT Raw Materials Summit (every year around April/May)	-	15/05/2023	17/05/2023	Physical	https://www.eitrawsummit.com/	Brussels (Belgium)	Raw materials/mining							
Arminera	1.67	22/05/2023	24/05/2023	Physical	https://arminera.ar.messefrankfurt.com/bu	Buenos Aires (Argentina)	Energy, Transport & logistic, Mining Technology and industrial fairs							ASGMI
3rd START Webinar (LNEG)	1	31/05/2023	31/05/2023	Online									LNEG	
European Sustainable Energy Week and EUSEW Fair	1.00	20/06/2023	22/06/2023	Hybrid	https://sustainable-energy-week.ec.europa.eu/	Brussels (Belgium)	Energy and Environment	Yes	-				EPMA	8000
Annual International Conference on Thermolectrics (ICT)	1.00	21/06/2023	25/06/2023	Physical	https://web.cvent.com/event/89985a9c-7d	Seattle (USA)	Thermolectrics							
Jornadas Científico Técnicas del IGME-CSIC	1.00	2023, Jun?			www.csic.es							Ester Boixereu	IGME	
Sustainable Minerals '23	n.d.	07/06/2023	09/06/2023	Physical	https://mei.eventsair.com/sustainable-min	Falmouth (UK)	Raw materials/mining							
Euronanoforum2023	1.67	11/06/2023	13/06/2023	Physical	https://mkn.nu/euro_nano_forum_2023	Malmö (Sweden)								
EPMA FM seminar 2023	1.00	28/06/2023	29/06/2023	Hybrid	seminars.epma.com	San Sebastián (Spain)	PM community	-	-	Technical pres		?	EPMA	
PM/AM/Metform on PM materials for Energy	1.00	05/07/2023	07/07/2023	Physical		Dresden (Germany)	PM community	-	-	Technical pres		?	EPMA	
European Roundtable on Sustainable Consumption and Production	n.d.	05/07/2023	08/07/2023	Physical	https://www.scp-conference-2023.com/w	Wageningen, NL	Academic, wide						LNEG	
EPMA Summer School 2023	1.00	17/07/2023	21/07/2023	Physical	https://summerschool.epma.com/	Dresden (Germany)	PM community	-	-	The START project/PM thermolectrics		A. Bianchini (MBN)	EPMA	
RawMat 2023	n.d.	28/08/2023	02/09/2023	Physical	https://www.rawmat2023.gr/congress/	Athens (Greece)								
Science/Business Green Deal & Climate days	n.d.	18/09/2023	19/09/2023	Hybrid	https://sciencebusiness.net/events/research	Brussels (Belgium)								
European Conference on Thermolectrics (ECT) 2023	1.00	18/09/2023	21/09/2023	Physical	https://thermolectric-conference.eu/	Prague, CZ	Thermolectric Academic							
SPM event - Materials for Energy Transition	n.d.	06/09/2023	08/09/2023	Physical	https://smaterials.pt/site/materials-for-er	Oporto, P	Materials			Presentation	07/09/2023	Maarten Den Heijer José Brito Correia	RGS LNEG	
Researchers' Night 2023	n.d.	29/09/2023	30/09/2023	Hybrid	https://marie-skłodowska-curie-actions.ec	Many	Academic, wide	-	-	Starty, leaflets, posters		?	LPRC, LNEG	
EuroPM23	n.d.	01/10/2023	04/10/2023	Physical	www.europm2023.com	Lisbon (Portugal)	PM community	Yes	-	Technical presentation	03/10/2023	J. Brito Correia (LNEG)	EPMA	
EU Supercluster Lapland Geocoference	1.00	30/10/2023	31/10/2023	Physical	https://eis-he.eu/clustering-event/	Rovaniemi (Finland)	Raw materials/mining	No		Technical presentation	?	G. Olivenza	ASGMI	100?
Raw Materials Week 2023	n.d.	13/11/2023	17/11/2023	Physical	https://www.rawmaterialsweek2023.eu/	Brussels (Belgium)	Raw materials/mining	No		poster, video			LPRC	
GENERA 2024 (International Energy and Environment Fair)	n.d.	06/02/2024	08/02/2024	Physical	https://www.ifema.es/en/genera	Madrid	Energy and Environment							
4th START Webinar (LNEG)	n.d.	2024, Feb?		Online									LNEG	
PDAC 2024: The World's Premier Mineral Exploration & Mining Convention	1.00	03/03/2024	06/03/2024	Physical	https://www.pdac.ca/convention	Toronto (Canada)	Raw materials/mining						LNEG	
TMS 2024 Annual Meeting & Exhibition	1.00	03/03/2024	07/03/2024	Physical	https://www.tms.org/AnnualMeeting/TMS	Orlando (USA)	Materials	?		Technical presentation		P. Carvalho	SINTEF	
EGU - European Geoscience Union (every year around April/May)	-	Apr-May 24		Physical	https://www.egu.eu/	Vienna (Austria)	Raw materials/mining							
EIT Raw Materials Summit (every year around April/May)	-	Apr-May 24		Physical	https://www.eitrawsummit.com/	Brussels (Belgium)	Raw materials/mining							
Hannover Messe 2024 (ENERGIZING A SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRY)		22/04/2024	26/04/2024	Physical	https://www.hannovermesse.de/en/	Hannover (Germany)								
Conference on Industrial Technologies IndTech 2024	n.d.	03/06/2024	05/06/2024	Physical		Namur (Belgium)								
START Seminar	n.d.	2024, Jun?		Physical	START website	TBD				Project pres		Many		
40th International & 20th European Conference on Thermolectrics (ICT/ECT) 2024	1.00	30/06/2024	04/07/2024	Physical	https://ict2024.agh.edu.pl/en	Krakow (Poland)	Thermolectric Academic					Maarten Den Heijer	RGS	

Figure 44: Status of the START Events List Excel file (updated 13/11/2023), section concerning the period between January 2023 and June 2024. In light green the events covered.

The tool is updated about upcoming events, reassessing the priorities continuously. In general, some high priority recurring events are these:

- European Conference on Thermoelectrics (ECT) conference series
- GENERA (International Energy and Environment Fair)
- Raw Materials Week
- EIT Raw Materials summit
- EU Sustainable Energy Week
- EU Green week
- EPMA's EuroPM Powder Metallurgy yearly Congress & Exhibition (was World PM in 2022)
- EPMA's seminars (HIP, Functional Materials)
- Sustainable Minerals
- In general, when partners have large internal events, these will be covered.

6.2 EVENTS COVERED IN M13-M18

The consortium continued to take part in events organised by third parties, where for the moment only very little scientific information on the achievements within the project could be disseminated. The partners most involved in the industrial side and generally the consortium preferred to postpone participation in industrial events like trade fairs, more related to the application, to later years in the project, when more practical achievements could be shown in order to attract interest.

Thus, most of these activities can still be considered a mix of communication and actual dissemination, for the moment.

6.2.1 ARMINERA mining fair, 22nd-24th May 2023, Buenos Aires (Argentina)

Since 1997, the Argentine Chamber of Mining Companies (CAEM) has been organizing the ARMINERA International Exhibition. This year, the event took place on 22nd-24th May 2023, in Buenos Aires.

Figure 45: Logo of the ARMINERA mining fair 2023.

Within the framework of the ARMINERA Fair, the 2023 edition of the *EU-Latin America Convention on Raw Materials and the 2nd EU-Latin America Policy Dialogue on the identification of strategic and critical raw materials resources* was held, focusing on the theme of Promoting EU-LATAM Investments in Sustainable Value Chains for Raw Materials.

Stakeholders along the entire raw materials value chain, from exploration and extraction to refining and recycling, as well as key players in subsequent phases contributing significantly to the clean

energy transition, gathered in Buenos Aires during those days. The Convention also brought together policymakers, industry representatives, the private sector, and stakeholders from research and innovation in the EU and LATAM.

The event kicked off with a high-level political session featuring representatives from seven Latin American countries and the European Commission and more than 250 participants.

Following this session, various panels were held to address diverse topics aimed at fostering collaboration along mineral supply chains between the EU and Latin America.

The Convention was organized by the EU-Latin America Partnership on Raw Materials project, funded by the European Union (EU). The project, initiated in 2018, aimed to promote and enhance cooperation between EU Member States and seven associated Latin American countries (Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Mexico, Peru, and Uruguay) along the value chains of mineral-based industries. Building on complementarities, common goals, and shared values between the EU and Latin America, the project seeks to take a step further in integrating strategic industrial value chains for both regions, exploring new business models, and adding value to society while maintaining the high environmental and social standards that form the core of this collaboration.

Throughout the Convention, in the fair, where there were over 200 exhibitors, information about START project (video presentation) was available at the booth of the "EU-LATAM Mining Platform" where members of the consortium (ASGMI, IGME-CSIC) were also present.

Note: although this event happened in the period covered by D6.4, it was impossible to add its description in that deliverable due to the time constraints for reviewing before submission.

Figure 46: Members of Expert Groups on Mineral Resources, Mining Environmental Liabilities and Geochemistry of ASGMI and IGME in the EU-Latin America Convention on Raw Materials (Buenos Aires, 2023)

6.2.2 *START lecture at the 21st EPMA Summer School in Dresden, 21st July 2023*

The EPMA Powder Metallurgy Summer School¹⁷ is organised by the European Powder Metallurgy Association (EPMA) with support from its members, since 1998, and about 1000 young graduates from both industry and academia from all over Europe have attended these summer schools, that give them advanced teaching of PM's advantages and limitations by some of the leading academic

¹⁷ <https://summerschool.epma.com/>

and industrial personnel in Europe, allowing them also to create their own network in the community, with peers and experienced lecturers.

The 2023 edition, the 21st in the series, was held in Dresden, Germany, from 17th to 21st July. 59 trainees took part.

Two activities involved the project.

Firstly, START was briefly presented by B. Vicenzi (EPMA) during his opening speech on Monday 17th July (Figure 47), as had already happened in 2022 in the 20th edition in Ciudad Real (Spain).

Secondly, and more importantly, on Friday 21st, 13:00 – 13:30, A. Bianchin (MBN) closed the lectures by giving a presentation titled “Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project” (Figure 48, Figure 49).

Figure 47: Highlights of the START project presented by B. Vicenzi of EPMA during the opening presentation at the 21st EPMA PM Summer School in Dresden, Germany

Figure 48: A. Bianchin (MBN) presenting “Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project” at the 21st EPMA PM Summer School in Dresden, Germany.

Figure 49: A. Bianchin (MBN) presenting “Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project” at the 21st EPMA PM Summer School in Dresden, Germany.

It is noteworthy that among the several lectures there were topics that are relevant for START (“Powder Manufacturing and Characterization”, “Alternative Methods and Innovative Sintering”, “Sustainability in Powder Metallurgy”).

As this activity is actually part of the Training task (D6.3), more details on this event will be given in the relevant deliverable, D6.8, that is due in May 2024 (M24).

START will feature again in the 22nd edition that will take place in Alessandria (Italy) in July 2024, possibly in a new format, as a lab experience.

6.2.3 *START lecture at the 2nd edition of Summer School “Materials for Energy Transition” in Porto, 7th September 2023*

The 2nd edition of the “Materials for Energy Transition” Summer School was a three-day event organised by Sociedade Portuguesa de Materiais (SPM), Ordem dos Engenheiros Região Norte, INL and LNEG. It took place in Porto on 6-8th September 2023.

Figure 50: Banner of the 2nd Edition of the “Materials for Energy Transition” Summer School, Porto (PT), 6-8 September 2023.

An oral presentation entitled “Projeto START – Utilização de tetraedrites como material termoelétrico” (“START Project – Use of tetrahedrites as thermoelectric material”) was given by José Brito Correia (LNEG) on 7th September to 20 Portuguese PhD and Master’s students in the session dedicated to “Advanced Energy Materials” (Figure 51). The lecture included an introduction to mechanochemical synthesis, spark plasma sintering and the use of tetrahedrites for thermoelectric applications. This was an excellent opportunity to publicize the project’s activities among the student community.

Figure 51: Presentation by José Brito Correia (LNEG) at the 2nd edition of the Summer School “Materials For Energy Transition” in Porto, 7th September 2023.

At the end of the session Filipe Neves (LNEG) participated in the round table where he had the opportunity to frame the project’s objectives within the current challenges associated with the energy transition and the indispensable contribution of materials.

As this activity is actually part of the Training task (D6.3), more details on this event will be given in the relevant deliverable, D6.8, that is due in May 2024 (M24).

Figure 52 Round table including Filipe Neves (LNEG) at the 2nd edition of the Summer School “Materials For Energy Transition” in Porto, 7th September 2023.

6.2.4 ECT 2023, 17th–21st September 2023, Prague (Czech Republic)

The 19th European Conference on Thermoelectric (ECT) brought together approximately 300 participants from academic institutions and industries, all dedicated to solid-state power generation applications. During the conference, valuable connections were established with notable figures such as Prof. Johannes Boor from DLR, Dr. Kanishka Biswas from JNCASR Bangalore, and representatives from various EU consortium projects with similarities to START, including ICARUS.

Figure 53: Banner for ECT 2023.

On the technical front, discussions revolved around protective coatings on tetrahedrite materials, crucial for the fabrication of the START module. The presentation by A. Ray of RGS, titled "**Feasibility of a Low-Power RTG Concept Utilizing a GPHS Heat Source,**" provided an industrial perspective on thermoelectric applications for both space and terrestrial use. Regarding the latter, RGS emphasized the importance of stable thermoelectric materials capable of performing well at a high operating temperature (T_{HOT}) of 400°C.

To address this specific requirement, RGS introduced our EU project during the speech, highlighting that START focuses on repurposing mine waste materials into thermoelectric modules, catering to the niche demand for stable materials that can operate at intermediate temperatures with high efficiency. The presentation received positive feedback from over 50 attendees, and they were encouraged to explore START's webpage for additional insights through webinars.

Applications

RGS experience:

Challenge: Many industrial waste heat applications from practical experience lead to a hot side temperature of 400-450C

- To date:
 - High temperature (Silicon germanium stable in air)
 - Low Temperature (Bi_2Te_3 stable in air)
 - Mid temperature (many variations, limited stability reported)
- Novel materials could also be tailored to benefit applications in space if matured
- Open question for research community: stable materials at these temperature ranges which have been tested at the module level

<https://www.startheproject.com/>

Figure 54: Slide from A. Ray (RGS) presentation at ECT2023.

EU START Project

- Source of P-type tetrahedrites material
- Waste sulphide mine dumps/tailling
 - Synthetic

Circular feed supply of raw materials

In the EU-funded START project looking at a combination of **P-type tetrahedrites** coupled with a suitable N-type thermoelectric element

<https://www.startheproject.com/>

Figure 55: Slide from A. Ray (RGS) presentation at ECT2023.

Figure 56: Delegates at ECT 2023.

Figure 57: Delegates at ECT 2023.

6.2.5 ASGMI Webinar “Copper Geology in Latin America”, 27th-28th September

On 27th-28th September 2023, the Ibero-American Geological and Mining Services Association (ASGMI) hosted a webinar on copper geology in Ibero-America. The webinar, organized by ASGMI's Expert Group on Metallogeny and Mineral Resources, featured prestigious speakers from different Ibero-American countries who discussed a variety of topics related to copper mining, including copper deposits in different parts of Ibero-America, the geology of copper deposits, the uses of copper and the reuse of environmental liabilities from copper mining. Copper is rapidly becoming a more demanded material due to the changes in energy and transportation models. The webinar was therefore intended to inform about different aspects of the copper mining industry, as

well as the latest research and developments in this field. It was held in Spanish and the relevant footage can be viewed on YouTube¹⁸.

Ester Boixereu, from the Geological and Mining Institute of Spain (IGME-CSIC), gave a presentation named “Reaprovechamiento de pasivos ambientales de la minería del cobre. El caso del proyecto START” (“Reuse of environmental liabilities from copper mining. The case of the START project”).

Figure 58: Banner of the webinar “La Geología del Cobre en Iberoamérica”, held on 27th-28th September 2023 by ASGMI.

¹⁸ <https://youtu.be/PFpbmHLTpDo>

Figure 59: Two moments from the presentation by Ester Boixereu (IGME) during the ASGMI Webinar “Copper Geology in Latin America”.

6.2.6 START in 2023 European Researchers’ Night Events

Also in 2023, the project took part in events of the European Researchers’ Night, that happened simultaneously on 29th September all over Europe, with many local events. Being an open event, the activities on this occasion can be rightly considered as Communication rather than Dissemination, although the audience can occasionally be interested in more scientific explanations.

Under the umbrella of the European Researchers’ Night of the Macaronesia¹⁹, the START project was featured in the MacaroNight 2023 digital EU Corner and the physical EU Corners in Tenerife

¹⁹ “Macaronesia consists of four main archipelagos. From north to south, these are 1) the Azores, an Autonomous Region of Portugal; 2) Madeira (including the Savage Islands), an Autonomous Region of Portugal; 3) the Canary Islands, an Autonomous Community of Spain; 4) Cape Verde, an independent West African country”. Text taken from Wikipedia, consulted on 11/11/2023, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Macaronesia>

and in the Patent's Week (2nd-6th October) in Gran Canaria. Copies of Starty's comics were printed by LPRC and distributed. Here are some data of the event:

- Digital EU Corner: 52.800 views
- EU Corner Tenerife: 3.000 participants – 400 comics copies
- Patents Week Gran Canaria: 500 participants – 100 comics copies
- Upcoming social media campaign highlighting the projects November to December

Figure 60: Banner of the “Macaronight” event that took place in Macaronesia on the occasion of the European Researchers’ Night on 29th September 2023.

Figure 61: In the “Macaronight”, START material was distributed.

START also took part in the European Researchers Night in Lisbon.

Figure 62: Banner of the “Macaronight” event that took place in Macaronesia on the occasion of the European Researchers' Night on 29th September 2023.

Figure 63: START material available at the European Researchers Night in Lisbon.

6.2.7 Booth and presentations at Euro PM2023 in Lisbon, Portugal, 01-04 October 2023

Like every year, EPMA hosted its annual European Congress & Exhibition. This year, it was organised in Lisbon, from 1st to 4th October²⁰. It has to be noted that the event of the previous year, the World PM2002 in Lyon, was then a world congress by a long-running agreement of EPMA with the parallel associations in America and Asia (the world congress happens every two years, but it changes continent every edition, so it is organised in Europe by EPMA every 6 years, “upgrading” the yearly Euro PM event - the next European World PM event will be in 2028).

About 800 delegates could follow a plenary session, about 70 technical sessions and visit the exhibition with more than 80 exhibitors.

Figure 64: Banner of Euro PM2023 Congress & Exhibition (Lisbon, Portugal, 01-04 October 2023)

Like in 2022, START organised a booth with informative posters and banners, a collection of exhibits (minerals, powders, an example of thermoelectric generator device) and a screen where the START introductory video and the latest Starty comic strip with explanations about the role of the project in pursuing the objectives of the EU in terms of efficient use of resources were displayed.

²⁰ <https://europm2023.com/>

Figure 65: The START booth at the Euro PM2023 Congress & Exhibition in Lisbon.

Figure 66: The display with samples and the screen with the running Starty comics.

Figure 67: Detail of the START display in the booth at Euro PM2023.

In the morning of Tuesday 3rd October, four twenty-minute demonstrations of the START project were held by José Brito Correia (LNEG) for international doctoral and master's students at the project booth. The attendees were participants of the EPMA's Young Engineers programme²¹. IN this programme, 48 students were hosted free of charge in the first 2 days of the congress and were given introductory lectures and a guided tour in the exhibition, including the START booth. These demonstrations featured a general description of the project and the presentation of materials and devices within the scope of thermoelectric materials, arousing great interest on the part of the students.

²¹ <https://www.youngengineers.epma.com/>

Figure 68: Demonstration of the START project to students of the Young Engineers programme during Euro PM2023, by J.B. Correia (LNEG).

On Tuesday afternoon, at 16:30, a 30' oral presentation entitled "Replacement of tellurium in thermoelectric materials" was given by José Brito Correia in Session 44: Functional Materials Special Interest Seminar – "Sustainability of Critical Raw Materials by PM".

Figure 69: Presentation of J.B. Correia (LNEG) in Session 44: Functional Materials Special Interest Seminar – "Sustainability of Critical Raw Materials by PM", during the Euro PM2023.

In addition to these specific activities, the two Technical Managers of EPMA B. Vicenzi and K. Boz, gave short introductions to the project during the 6 Sectoral Group meetings (EuroAM, EuroFM, EuroMIM, Euro Press&Sinter, EuroHM, EuroHIP) and a Working Group meeting (EHQS) held in the Congress.

The full programme of the event is available in the event website.

6.2.8 EU Supercluster Event Lapland, 30th-31st October 2023, Rovaniemi (FI)

EU SUPERCLUSTER LAPLAND GEOCONFERENCE

JOIN MULTIPLE EU-FUNDED MINERAL RAW MATERIALS PROJECTS FOR A ONE-AND-A-HALF-DAY CLUSTERING EVENT TO DISCUSS & EXCHANGE IDEAS ON CURRENT TECHNOLOGICAL CHALLENGES AND TOPICS WITHIN THE RAW MATERIALS SECTOR.

CALL FOR: ORAL AND POSTER PRESENTATIONS
PRESENT YOUR RESEARCH OR PROJECT!

30-31 OCT.
2023

ROVANIEMI
FINLAND

REGISTER NOW FOR FREE

Figure 70: Banner of the EU Supercluster Lapland geoconference.

Thirteen EU-funded raw materials projects EIS, AGEMERA, CIRAN, EXCEED, GOLDENEYE, GREENPEG, M4MINING, MaDiTraCe, MinExTarget, MultiMiner, S34I, SEEMS DEEP and SEMACRET, as well as the University of Queensland (Australia) were partnering up to organize a one-and-a-half-day clustering event “European Union SuperCluster Lapland Geoconference”, which took place on Monday 30th and Tuesday 31st October 2023 in Rovaniemi, Finland.

This event brought together a wide range of stakeholders, such as the European Commission, EU projects and other initiatives related to the raw materials sector; regional authorities; industrial representatives; exploration companies as well as other interested stakeholders, to discuss and exchange ideas on current technological challenges and topics within the sector.

The SuperCluster event was organized just before the official start of the 14th Fennoscandian Exploration and Mining (FEM) 2023 conference (Levi, Kittilä, Finland)²², one of the most significant and largest mining industry events in Europe.

Gracia Olivenza from the Ibero-American Geological and Mining Services Association (ASGMI) attended the event as a speaker (speech title: “Reusing Secondary Mineral Resources For The Energy Transition: The Project START Example”, hosted in Session 5 “New frontiers for exploration”) and had the opportunity to provide a 15-minute presentation overviewing the project’s objectives and key impacts. The event, with over 140 participants, served as a meeting point for various projects dedicated to innovation in the exploration and acquisition of mineral resources. Additionally, discussions encompassed topics related to sustainability, the environment, and social license or acceptance. Abstracts of the event can be downloaded²³.

²² www.femconference.fi

²³ https://tupa.gtk.fi/raportti/arkisto/55_2023.pdf

It was a great opportunity to learn about innovative techniques and engage with other professionals in the industry on making mining activities more efficient and sustainable and how to make the projects we participate in more visible.

Figure 71: EU Supercluster Lapland geoconference.

6.2.9 Raw Materials Week, 13th-17th November 2023, Brussels (BE)

The START project was also showcased during the EU Raw Materials Week 2023, a yearly event (the project was already showcased during the 2022 edition). The Raw Materials Week gathers a wide range of stakeholders discussing policies and initiatives in the field of raw materials, providing an overview of ongoing EU activities in the sector.

Figure 72: Banner of the Raw Materials Week 2023.

START had its introductory video, with the addition of the Starty comic (issue #2), and poster displayed in the event, where stakeholders could watch and learn more about the project's objectives and actions.

Figure 73: START video displayed during the Raw Materials Week 2023.

6.3 EVENTS IN PREPARATION

In the next months, participation in some events has already been imagined. We would like to prepare for some important thermoelectrics and energy events, in additions to those on raw materials

- ASGMI Mining Environmental Liabilities Workshop, Brazil 27th November -1st December 2023: ASGMI organises this event in which some consortium collaborators will be present and F. Guzmán (Mexican Geological Service, who has collaborated on WP2, will include a couple of slides about START in his presentation. More details in the next deliverable.
- In the next TMS 2024 Annual Meeting and Exhibition, an international event on materials, an abstract has already been submitted²⁴ and approved for the Symposium “Advanced Materials for Energy Conversion and Storage 2024”. Patricia Carvalho (SINTEF) is set as presenter.

²⁴ Filipe Neves, Anna Lind, Serena Busatti, Konstantina Iordanidou, Alvis Bianchin, Marcin Rosinski, Patricia Carvalho, Jose Brito Correia: “Composition optimization of tetrahedrites for enhanced thermoelectric performance through design of experiments”, <https://www.programmaster.org/PM/PM.nsf/ApprovedAbstracts/55A2A9FD02AC1941852589DF00818F32?OpenDocument>

THE WORLD COMES HERE.

TMS 2024

153rd Annual Meeting & Exhibition

Figure 74: Banner of TMS 2024.

THE WORLD COMES HERE.
TMS 2024
 153rd Annual Meeting & Exhibition

MARCH 3-7, 2024
 HYATT REGENCY ORLANDO
 ORLANDO, FLORIDA, USA
 #TMSAnnualMeeting

SUBMIT AN ABSTRACT FOR THE FOLLOWING TMS2024 SYMPOSIUM:

ELECTRONIC, MAGNETIC, AND ENERGY MATERIALS

Advanced Materials for Energy Conversion and Storage 2024

Theme 1: Energy Conversion
 These focus area topics include, but are not limited to experiments and modeling of energy conversion systems, including:

- SOFCs and reversible SOFCs/SOECs
- PEM fuel cells
- The durability of the fuel cell and stack materials
- Degradation due to thermo-mechanical-chemical effects
- Effect of microstructure evolution on the properties and efficiency
- Chromium poisoning from interconnections and Balance of Plant
- Advances in characterization and modeling techniques for energy generation systems include AI, big data, and Deep Learning

Theme 2: Energy Storage
 Focus areas include:

- Batteries
- Physicochemical interaction in intercalation, conversion, and metal batteries, e.g., lithium-ion, solid-state, Na-ion, Li-S, Li-air
- Electrode microstructure - property - performance interplay
- Mesoscale modeling and characterization (e.g., X-ray tomography)
- Degradation (e.g., mechanical, chemical, electrodeposition) and safety characteristics in electrodes
- Computer simulation/modeling includes AI, big data, and deep learning

Theme 3: Materials Design for Sustainability and Energy Harvesting
 This symposium component will focus on a variety of green and sustainable technologies for energy harvesting, additive manufacturing, green tribology, next-generation products and processes, and development of advanced instrumentation and control systems, etc.

Proposed Session Topics:

- Solar Energy
- Wind Energy
- Supercapacitor
- Additive manufacturing, 3D printing, and sustainability
- Green Tribology

Theme 4: Functional Materials, including Coating, Ceramics, and Alloys
 Focus areas include:

- Functional Oxides, Nitrides, and Carbides
- Ceramics and Dielectrics
- Sensors
- Thermal Energy Harvesting, Conversion, storage, and Management Devices
- Functional Coatings for Harsh Environments
- Nanotechnology and Multifunctional Materials
- Membrane Separation Materials, Processes, and Systems (H₂, O₂, CO₂)
- Water Splitting and Other Catalyst Applications
- In-Situ Spectroscopy and Advanced Characterization of Functional Materials
- Harsh Environment Electromagnetic Materials
- Computer simulation/modeling includes AI, big data, and deep learning

This symposium intends to provide a forum for researchers from national laboratories, universities, and industry to discuss the current understanding of materials science issues in advanced materials for energy conversion and storage, including high-temperature processes, and to discuss accelerating the development and acceptance of innovative materials, and test techniques for clean energy technology.

ORGANIZERS
 Jung Chok, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, USA
 Amit Pandey, Lockheed Martin Space, USA
 Partha Mukherjee, Purdue University, USA
 Surajit Gupta, University of North Dakota, USA
 Soumenendra Basu, Boston University, USA
 Paul Ohodnicki, University of Pittsburgh, USA
 Eric Detsi, University of Pennsylvania, USA

SYMPOSIUM SPONSORS
 TMS Functional Materials Division
 TMS Energy Conversion and Storage Committee

www.tms.org/TMS2024

QUESTIONS?
 Contact programming@tms.org

Figure 75: Symposium “Advanced Materials for Energy Conversion and Storage 2024” at TMS2024.

- START will feature again in the 22nd edition that will take place in Alessandria (Italy) in July 2024, possibly in a new format, as a lab experience.
- A booth will be booked at the EPMA Euro PM2024 Congress & Exhibition that will be held in Malmö (Sweden), from 29th September to 2nd October 2024, with some more effort compared to 2023 and hopefully some results could be shown. Participation with a technical presentation is also possible; a specific session, a workshop, could be imagined, comprising participation from other projects (e.g., THERMOS) linked in the Clustering activity.

The consortium is also considering the possibility of participating in fairs, like the Genera 2024 and/or the Hannover Messe 2024, and will consider trying again to join the EU Sustainable Energy Week exhibition. We have also been invited to an ERHASE session in the InComEss final meeting in January 2024 (see chapter 8.1.3), and to take part in the next ECT/ICT (European and also International Conference on Thermoelectrics) that will be next year in Krakow. Later in 2024, we

also want to take a more active role in the Raw Materials Week (November, Brussels), and might propose a side event there.

Other smaller events where project partners will bring information and short presentations about the project will surely be attended.

6.4 PUBLICATIONS

In the first months of the project, as documented in Deliverables 6.3 and 6.4, a few documents had already been produced for publication.

Publications that have been uploaded on the website and on the Zenodo open access repository, where a “community” named “Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling” was created, obtained a specific DOI, and they have automatically been added in the Continuous Reporting Publications page in the Funding & Tender portal for the project (see chapter 5.7.3).

In addition to this, publications on magazines, as reported in the following chapters, have not been uploaded to Zenodo, yet they are fully readable online, with open access, in the magazines’ websites.

6.4.1 EPMA newsletters

As already detailed in chapter 5.2, EPMA published many internal newsletters with details on START.

6.4.2 START on the magazine “Powder Metallurgy Review”

As anticipated in deliverable D6.4, an article written by the consortium, with contributions from F. Neves (LNEG), B. Vicenzi (EPMA), A. Bianchin (MBN Nanomaterialia), M. Rosinski (GeniCore) and H. Yin (TEGnology) was published on the Spring 2023 issue (vol. 12, n.1, Figure 76) of the well-known powder metallurgical magazine Powder Metallurgy Review²⁵.

After a few months, the editor Inovar gave us some information on the impact of the publication of the Spring issue: 19000 reads (data communicated on 4th September). Clearly this does not imply that 19000 readers actually read the START article, so this is more of a “distribution” figure. Still, a rather high volume compared to the usual distribution of our material.

²⁵ <https://www.pm-review.com>

Figure 76: The Spring 2023 issue cover (Spring 2023, 112 pages) of the Powder Metallurgy Review printed and web magazine.

The full issue is published Open Access, and it is freely available for reading and downloading in pdf version²⁶ on the Powder Metallurgy Review website.

In September 2023 we published it on our website, and in November 2023 we also uploaded it to SlideShare. On Zenodo it had already been uploaded in March (22 views, 24 downloads as of 16/11/2023).

6.4.3 *START on the magazine “Ciência & Tecnologia dos Materiais” 2023 Vol.35 N°1*

An article written by F. Neves (LNEG), in Portuguese, has been published recently on the Portuguese magazine “Ciência & Tecnologia dos Materiais”²⁷ 2023 Vol.35 N°1 (Figure 77).

²⁶ <https://www.pm-review.com/powder-metallurgy-review-archive/powder-metallurgy-review-spring-2023-vol-12-no-1/>

²⁷ <https://spmateriais.pt/site/ciencia-tecnologia-dos-materiais/>

CIÊNCIA & TECNOLOGIA DOS MATERIAIS

Figure 77: “Ciência & Tecnologia dos Materiais 2023” Vol.35 Nº1, edited by the Portuguese Materials Society (SPM).

The text is a full review of the project features, and it is visible in full on the magazine website²⁸ and in Annex II.

6.4.4 Abstract of presentation “Reusing Secondary Mineral Resources For The Energy Transition: The Project START Example”

The abstract of the presentation given by G. Olivenza of ASGMI and coauthored by a many members of the consortium²⁹, has been uploaded on 16th November 2023 on Slideshare and will be uploaded to other platforms in the following days (see chapters 5.3.5 and 6.2.8 for more details).

²⁸ [OD0001992_revistaSPM_7aEdicao_V05_WEB_AF.pdf \(wop.com.pt\)](#)

²⁹ Filipe Neves, Daniel de Oliveira, Igor Morais, Luís Albardeiro (LNEG); Luís Lopes (LPRC), Bruno Vicenzi (EPMA), [Gracia Olivenza](#) (ASGMI), Fredy Guzmán (Servicio Geológico Mexicano, SGM), Stanislav Soltes (SGUDS), Thomas Unterweissacher (GEO), Piotr Lipiarski (Geosphere) and Ester Boixereu i Vila (IGME)

7 TASK 6.3: TRAINING ACTIVITIES

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M12 to M48

This task's activities started officially in May 2023, but details have been given in D6.5 (May 2023) and will be given in D6.8 (May 2024), that are dedicated to the training activities. Nevertheless, some activities (EPMA Summer School and SPM Summer School) have been mentioned elsewhere in this deliverable.

8 TASK 6.4: CLUSTERING

Task leader: ASGMI; Participants: All; M03 to M48

The objective of the clustering activity, that constitutes task T6.4 and began at M03 and will continue for the whole project duration to end at M48, is building a comprehensive cluster for the dissemination of the project. The main idea is to create an effective strategy to identify similar and interesting projects and find synergies to create value, avoid duplications and strengthen and maximize the START project results impact.

Projects that share a common theme or address similar challenges can form a cluster initiative and deliver shared strategic outputs. Thus, START wants to enhance links and synergies with such projects and initiatives. ASGMI with the support of all partners is identifying the project coordinators of the selected projects & initiatives. Mapping the synergies among the different projects will maximize the impact and contribute to have a more efficient and strong European Innovation.

A database has been created, which has been filled during this period with interesting initiatives and projects and will be kept updated throughout the rest of the project. Some of the resources consulted to feed this database are the following:

- The Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) for H2020 or Horizon Europe projects
- The EIT (including the KICs on Raw Materials, InnoEnergy & Climate KIC)
- The internal community (partners in the consortium and its members)

The links are being established by a series of online short meetings with the relevant Project Coordinators or key people and the START project coordinator and/or the Communication WP leader.

Key events and meetings are essential to identify and establish good connections: the people from the initiatives in the clustering database, likely belonging to the audience target Groups 2 and 3, but in some cases also from Group 1, will be invited to the relevant events organized by START (seminars, webinars, trainings, final event) ensuring dedicated time for networking and collaboration. Conversely, START consortium members participating to events are supposed to seek connections with all interesting stakeholders.

8.1 CLUSTERING STRATEGY

A clustering strategy has been designed in order to be implemented during the whole project duration. This strategy consists of two work lines: internal and external clustering:

8.1.1 Internal clustering

Consortium members are being contacted to identify projects, or other initiatives in which they are involved and/or are aware of, and check if they have common points and potential to establish synergies.

8.1.2 External clustering

The strategy for external clustering consists in contacting institutions and organizations that are not directly involved in the START project but work in similar or complementary themes.

These can be classified as explained in the next subchapters.

8.1.2.1 Key institutions and actors

Associations and big organizations directly or indirectly related to technical projects or other research initiatives are especially important because networks in which they are involved have a big potential for clustering with START project. They have a “helicopter view” of the activities done by their members and contacting them is a fast and easy way to reach a large number of potential projects.

Key people (outreach people and project leaders) in these organizations have been identified and contacted in order to schedule meetings between projects or Work Package leaders.

Clustering task and communication leaders of the project contacted key individuals at EIT Raw Materials, InnoEnergy KICs, and EuroGeoSurveys during the previous reporting period. Additionally, contact has been established and meetings held with other initiatives and organizations, which are detailed in the following sections.

8.1.2.1.1 ERHASE Cluster meeting

During this period, on October 2023 a meeting with the ERHASE Cluster initiative took place. The ERHASE Cluster is formed by three European Projects (FAST-SMART, SYMPHONY, InComEss) with the aim to address the technical scope areas within the context of energy harvesting and storage technologies. Through the cluster, participating projects may expand their impact beyond the project level, while contributing to the dissemination of state-of-the-art research and developments. Together, the 3 projects will boost awareness regarding the research outcomes and promote energy harvesting with relevant stakeholders, such as academia and industry.

At the meeting with representatives from the three projects that are part of ERHASE, the possibility of START joining the initiative was discussed. Since the three projects comprising ERHASE conclude in February, March, and April of next year, it does not seem possible to organize future joint initiatives. However, there is the possibility for START to attend one of the closing meetings of these projects.

After the meeting, internal discussions took place regarding potential avenues to continue the created cluster by incorporating other projects similar to START. The objective is to carry out joint initiatives such as virtual and/or in-person events that bring together a larger number of relevant attendees for the project.

8.1.2.1.2 THERMOS meeting

Through consortium members, two organizations participating in projects similar to START have been identified: the Fraunhofer Institute for Manufacturing Technology and Advanced Materials IFAM, and the Leibniz Institute for Solid State and Materials Research Dresden IFW.

Both institutions are conducting projects, in particular the THERMOS project³⁰, related to thermoelectricity, specifically researching the development of tellurium-free thermoelectric devices using alternative raw materials. Given the similarity of the projects being developed, it is proposed to organize, in addition to public outreach events where members of both organizations are invited as speakers, private meetings among specific members of the projects who can exchange experiences about the processes they are working on. It is decided to resume discussions at the end of November to finalize some of these initiatives.

8.1.2.2 Link with communication and dissemination activities

Project consortium members participation in technical or commercial big events, congress or other initiatives is interesting because this participation brings the opportunity to meet key people and find out new projects or initiatives related directly or indirectly with the project in order to stablish synergies.

To maximize the potential of clustering in these events, the clustering strategy builds a list of the events in which the consortium members are going to attend, identify potential organizations or key participants in the event and suggest to the consortium members to contact them before and during the events to talk about related projects. This list is actually included in the Events List for Dissemination and the most interesting events for clustering are given a higher priority.

8.1.2.3 CORDIS

CORDIS provides information on all EU-supported R&D activities, including programs (Horizon Europe, H2020, FP7 and older), projects, results and publications so is an essential platform for looking for projects under same or similar calls and finding out the coordinator to establish contact.

8.1.2.4 Clustering Database

The database listing the clustering actions has been updated (see chapter 8.1.3).

This database includes data such as the name or organization, contact person, date of meeting and comments related to experiences exchanged in the meeting.

8.1.2.5 Invite key actors to project meetings

Project meeting or events (virtual and in person) are good opportunities for inviting key actors (project leaders, researchers or stakeholders) to disseminate the objectives and advances in the project and try to establish synergies and common dissemination actions. Some of these researchers have been invited as speakers in the webinars organized by the project and have contributed to their dissemination and diffusion:

- Webinar #02 (26th April 2023):
 - Fredy Guzmán-Martínez (Servicio Geológico Mexicano)
 - Rafael Bittencourt Lima (Serviço Geológico do Brasil – CPRM)
- Webinar #03 (31st May 2023):
 - Doug Crane (DTP Thermoelectrics LLC, also member of START's Scientific Advisory Board)

³⁰ <https://www.m-era.net/materipedia/2021/thermos>

- Julie Hollies (EuroGeoSurveys, also member of START's Scientific Advisory Board)

Although no other specific event was organized in the last 6 months, more experts will be invited to the future events, also from the clusters and projects that we have been talking with.

8.1.3 *Clustering database*

As already mentioned, a clustering database has been created in order to achieve the objectives of the clustering strategy. The database is being updated with new organizations and projects and will remain active throughout the project.

At the moment, the database lists more than 40 projects that may have a connection with START. The key organizations and projects with which initial contact has been made or meetings have been held are included in the following table. As this deliverable is public, but the full list cannot be public for privacy issues, it is not shown here. Only stakeholder entities' names are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Key institutions and interesting related project identified for Clustering.

Organization	Meeting date	Projects	
EIT Raw Materials	16/11/2022	EuGeLi	https://eitrawmaterials.eu/project/eugeli/
		RIS-CuRE	RIS-CuRE: Zero waste recovery of copper tailings in the ESEE region - EIT RawMaterials
		BioLeach	BioLeach: Innovative Bio-treatment of RM - EIT RawMaterials
		INCO-Piles 2020	INCO-Piles-2020. International consortium to recover CRMs from stockpiles/tailings targeting RIS - EIT RawMaterials
EIT InnoEnergy	To be scheduled		
Fraunhofer Institute for Manufacturing Technology and Advanced Materials IFAM	18/10/2023	THERMOS	https://www.m-era.net/materipedia/2021/thermos
Leibniz institute for Solid State and Materials Research Dresden (IFW)			
H2020 and Horizon Europe Projects			
FutuRaM	To be scheduled	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058522	
FAST-SMART	8/10/2023 (ERHASE Clustering)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862289	
InComEss		https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862597/es	
Symphony		https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862095	

In addition to what reported in the table, the project GREENPEG that organised the Uppsala conference mentioned in D6.4, expressed the intention of inviting START to give information in a later webinar, to be defined. The project InComEss will celebrate a final workshop in early 2024 and START will likely join an ERHASE clustering session.

8.2 KEY EVENTS AND MEETINGS

During this period of the START project, the consortium members have participated in different events in which they have disseminated about the project, its main objectives and topics.

In these events, members have had the opportunity to seek connections with interesting stakeholders.

Main events, that have been described with more details in paragraph 6.2, are listed below:

- EU-Latin America Raw Materials Convention and 2nd EU-Latin America Policy Dialogue on the identification of strategic and critical raw materials resources, Buenos Aires (Argentina), 22nd –24th May 2023
- EPMA Summer School 2023 17th-21st July 2023
- SPM Summer School - Materials for Energy Transition 6th-8th September 2023
- European Conference on Thermoelectrics (ECT) 2023 18th-21st September 2023
- Researchers' Night 2023 29th-30th September 2023
- EuroPM2023 1st-4th October 2023
- EU Supercluster Lapland Geoconference 30th-31st October 2023
- Raw Materials Week 2023 13th-17th November 2023
- ASGMI Mining Environmental Liabilities Workshop, Brazil 27th November -1st December 2023

9 TASK 6.5: FINAL EVENT

Task leader: ASGMI; Participants: LNEG, All; M42 to M48

A final conference will be organised at the end of the project as a main dissemination event showcasing the successes achieved over the four years of the project.

The conference will likely take place in Brussels.

The details of the event (type of event, audience, keynote speakers...) will be determined during the project (starting around M42).

The final conference will try to be organised back-to-back with another mayor relevant event to ensure as large attendance as possible.

This task is not active yet. Nothing to report.

10 ANNEX I – START NEWSLETTER – ISSUE #3 – NOVEMBER 2022

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BIANNUAL NEWSLETTER OF THE START PROJECT | ISSUE 3

RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE
for a Sustainable Future

EDITORIAL

Dear members of the START community, Welcome to the third Biannual Newsletter of the START Project! We are happy to share with you some exciting results and updates from our Innovation activities.

It has been 17 months since we started this ambitious project to develop novel thermoelectric materials and devices from mine waste, and we have made significant progress in several areas.

One of the highlights of this issue is a new story board with Starty, our friendly mascot, that tells us something more about the tetrahedrite material and the use of powder technology in the project. You can learn more about the material and the technologies we are using in a fun and engaging way.

Our geology partners have also been busy identifying and characterizing relevant mine waste sites in Germany, so you will have some details on this task. In addition, we have updates on the progress we have made on synthesis, testing and integration of the thermoelectric materials.

Another important event that we want to revisit is the annual meeting that took place at IGME-CSIC in Madrid from May 30 to June 1. This was a great opportunity for all the partners to meet again face-to-face, exchange ideas, discuss challenges and plan future actions. We also had fruitful discussions with Doug Crane, one of our scientific advisory board members, who provided valuable feedback and guidance for our project.

We want to share with you some of the dissemination activities that we have carried out in the past months, such as the LCA (Life

Cycle Assessment) workshop given by our partner 3drivers, where we learned about the life cycle assessment methodology and how to apply it to our project. We participated in other dissemination events, such as the EPMA Summer School and Macaronight 2023, and continued our webinars series where we presented our project to a wider audience.

In this issue, we also have a Technical Pill where we address the use of machine-learning techniques to optimize thermoelectric properties in vast composition ranges. This is a very innovative and powerful approach that can help us discover new materials and improve existing ones.

This time we host an interesting interview with Jean-Yves Escabasse, one of the START Scientific Advisory Board members, who shares with us his insights and perspectives on thermoelectricity and its potential applications in various sectors. He also tells us about his experience and thoughts on the European research programmes.

Finally, we invite you to enjoy another leg in our consortium tour, where this time we meet ASGMI, the Association of Iberoamerican Geological and Mining Surveys, and GeniCore, an innovative company with expertise in SPS (Spark Plasma Sintering) technology. They are both key partners in our project and contribute to its success.

We hope you enjoy reading this newsletter and learning more about our project. We invite you to visit our website and follow us on social media for more updates. Thank you for your continued interest and support!

(F. Neves)

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Figure 78: START-Newsletter_Issue_3-page-001

START

NEWSLETTER

RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE for a Sustainable Future

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Figure 79: START-Newsletter_Issue_3-page-002

STARTY EXPLAINS START – 3: TETRAHEDRITE – THE MATERIAL

#3: TETRAHEDRITE - The Material

Figure 80: START-Newsletter_Issue_3-page-003

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HIGH ENERGY BALL MILLING

Figure 82: START-Newsletter_Issue_3-page-005

Figure 83: START-Newsletter_Issue_3-page-006

THE EFFORT FOR STARTY IN MANY LANGUAGES

If you read the previous newsletters or followed us on our social media accounts and the website, you already know Starty, that is usually the “frontrobot” of our communication. To make Starty more widely understandable, we made the effort of covering a large part of the EU official languages, and even more. We have made our comics author J. Mascarenhas (LNEG) work hard to deliver new versions of his comic strip involving the robot Starty first in twelve, and then in thirteen different languages!

He received the contribution from many of our consortium partners, with the translation of the original Starty strips (that you have seen in Issues 1 and 2 of our newsletter) into their mother tongues. All in all, we have collected the following localised versions: Catalan, Danish, German, English, Spanish, French, Italian, Dutch, Norwegian, Polish, Portuguese, Slovak, Turkish.

You can find the multilingual editions of “Starty explains START” on our website’s [Documents](#) page. Soon, also this third edition will be there for you, in your language!

Figure 1 - Starty loves Earth and knows your language too!

START CHRONICLES: GEOLOGY, THERMOELECTRICS AND MORE

NEWS FROM WORKPACKAGE 2 "SELECTION OF MINE WASTE SITES; PHYSICAL MINERAL SEPARATION AND CONCENTRATION: RELEVANT MINE WASTE SITES IN GERMANY"

Germany has a long tradition in the extraction and processing of different types of metal raw materials, as is reflected in the mining residues. There are over 2300 different dumps with residues from metal mining in Germany. The dumps include waste rock, processing residues, and slag, and vary in size from <math>< 1000 \text{ m}^3</math> to > 1000000 m^3. Most of the dumps are among the smaller ones (<math>< 5000 \text{ m}^3</math>). The database "Mindat.org" reports 238 mining locations with minerals of the tennantite-tetrahedrite series (the so-called "fahlores"; see [Figure 3a](#)).

In most of these locations, tetrahedrite is a subordinate mineral. In finding suitable mine waste sites for START, we initially focussed on three relatively large dumps with high contents of sulphide minerals. For these dumps, there could also be an additional environmental benefit in re-using the material, making secondary mining more profitable. The most interesting example would be the tailings dump of the Rammelsberg mine by Goslar (Harz Mountains) with approx. 7 million t tailings of which ca. 20% consists of sulphides (see [Figure 2](#)), 25% of barite, and 55% of carbonates and silicates [12].

Figure 2 - a) Sulphide-concentrate sample from the Rammelsberg tailings dump that was kindly made available for START by the REMINTA project consortium (<https://www.reminta.de>), and b) and c) photomicrographs showing the minerals ccp - chalcopyrite, gn - galena, and py - pyrite. XRD (X-Ray Diffraction) analysis revealed that the modal mineralogy of the sulphide concentrate consists mainly of pyrite (49 wt%), barite (10 wt%), muscovite (9 wt%), chlorite (5 wt%), galena (4 wt%), sphalerite (3 wt%), carbonate (10 wt%), feldspars (4%), and quartz (4%). The common accessory minerals are chalcopyrite, gypsum, and pyrrhotite.

However, discussions in the project consortium have made clear, that (1) large amounts of iron and lead are unfavourable for the development of suitable thermo-electric elements, and (2) that, in addition to fahlores, other minerals containing copper and antimony are also of interest for START. Therefore, an effort was made to compile a preliminary list of locations with dumps especially enriched in fahlore and/or antimony minerals (see **Figure 3b**). This work was based on **Figure 3a**, the data repositories [3, 4, 5, 6, 2, 8], and literature on ore deposits [e.g., 9, 10, 11, 12, for the Schwarzwald mining district]. We have sampled about 25 kg of material from four promising locations (e.g., Schmiedestollenhalde, Wittichen). Gangue minerals showing impregnated sulphide ores of various grain sizes dominate these samples. The samples are currently being analysed in our laboratories, using XRF (X-Ray Fluorescence), ore microscopy, and various SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) methods, in order to decide on further processing for use in START.

c) **Figure 3 - a)** Mining locations with minerals of the tennantite-tetrahedrite series (so-called "fahlores") in Germany according to mindat.org [4]; **b)** Possible mine waste locations especially enriched in minerals of the tennantite-tetrahedrite series (blue) and/or antimony (purple); **c)** Schmiedestollen dump by Wittichen (Schwarzwald Mining District).

Figure 86: START-Newsletter_Issue_3-page-009

NEWS FROM WORK PACKAGES “NEWS FROM THE LABS (WORK PACKAGES 3, 4, 5)”

Materials modelling and synthesis development has continued in these months on the quest to optimize the composition in terms of nature and amount of transition metal dopants (by DFT - Density Functional Theory²⁴ modelling), the production process (by Mechanochemical synthesis, MCS) and the sintering conditions (by Spark Plasma Sintering, SPS) for the p- and n-type thermoelectric materials meant to constitute the active core of the thermoelectric (TE) devices.

In order to evaluate the TE properties of MCS tetrahedrite powders with different dopant compositions (p-type material), they first need to be consolidated by SPS. TE properties strongly depend on the sintering parameters, since they contribute to the evolution of the microstructure obtained with the MCS, which in turns affect Seebeck coefficient (S), electrical (α) and thermal conductivity (κ).

For these reasons, systematic investigation of the SPS parameters was conducted, in particular of the sintering temperature, which led to identifying the conditions to obtain maximum densification (98-99% of the theoretical density). TE properties (Seebeck coefficient, electrical and thermal conductivity) were measured on several compacted samples (**Figure 4**) and this allowed to select both the most promising dopant composition and the optimum sintering conditions.

Figure 4 - (left) Tetrahedrite samples after SPS compaction. (right) Assembly of a sample for the Seebeck coefficient and electrical resistivity tests in the LZT-Meter from Linseis.

Larger batches were produced with an optimized composition, and many identical tiles were sintered to assemble the first START TE devices (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5 - Photos of the graphite mold and of the sintered tiles of purely synthetic tetrahedrites obtained by SPS, that will be used for the production of the first TE device of the START project. The dimensions of the tiles are 23x23x2.5 mm.

Having optimized the synthetic tetrahedrite composition, we focused then on the actual goal of the START project, that is to incorporate as much mineral concentrate from mine tailing as possible in the tetrahedrite formulation. First promising results have come also from this front, in particular in the case of samples containing as much as 50% of mineral tetrahedrite a high zT value⁴⁴ was measured, close to that of purely synthetic tetrahedrites with optimized composition (0.51 vs 0.49 at 350 °C).

TE devices can only function with both p-type and n-type legs, and, since there is no known n-type tetrahedrites, we have conducted extensive literature research and discussions among the partners to identify a suitable n-type material. The selection has been done considering the compatibility on three main parameters: 1) working temperature, 2) electric properties, and 3) thermal expansion. Eventually, $Mg_{0.245}Sb_{2-x}Bi_x$ has been selected since its temperature of peak zT can be tuned to match the range of tetrahedrites' by adjusting the Sb/Bi ratio, the thermal expansion differences can be managed on the device engineering, and it does not contain rare or toxic elements.

The mechanochemical synthesis of this material poses several challenges to be addressed:

(1) Mg has a very low vapour pressure, so part of it could easily evaporate during the consolidation, resulting in a Mg-deficient material;

(2) when x is higher than 0.5, a further Mg-excess is needed to avoid having unalloyed Bi;

(3) it has p-type character if not appropriately doped.

Keeping all this in mind, a first series of MCS powder materials has been produced and it is now on its way to be sintered.

START FIRST ANNUAL MEETING IN MADRID

The START consortium got together from 30th May to 1st of June 2023 for its first Annual Meeting, the second general meeting after the Kick-Off that had happened in Lisbon in June 2022. The event took place in a quite inspiring venue: the Museo Geominero in Madrid, Spain, that was offered by our partner, IGME-CSIC. The meeting was jointly organized by IGME and ASGMI.

Surrounded by an impressively huge collection of rocks, minerals and fossils, the consortium met in the museum's lecture room for three days. Workshops open to the whole consortium were led by the various Work Package leaders; the activities already undertaken, their results, and especially the decisions on how to proceed towards project's objectives were discussed. Some special meetings were dedicated to critical issues, and solutions and strategies were analysed, benefiting of the in-person situation. Doug Crane, one of the members of our Scientific Advisory Board, took a long trip from the US to Spain to join us, and he was also involved as speaker in the hybrid live webinar that was held in the afternoon of the 31st of May (read about that below).

The group also enjoyed conviviality, in the lunch and coffee breaks in the museum's historical rooms, and during a nice consortium dinner in down-town Madrid.

The 2nd Annual Meeting, next year, will be in Italy! Venice awaits us!

Figure 6 - The START consortium partners that were present in Madrid for the first Annual Meeting (only the partner who took the picture is missing).

Figure 7 - The main hall of the Museo Geominero of Madrid, that hosted the first Annual Meeting of START.

Figure 8 - Tetrahedrite samples (at the back) are present in the sulphides section of the museum's exhibition.

Figure 9 - Meetings for specific subjects ran in parallel during the Annual Meeting.

START WEBINAR #3

As you may remember, we already have given you information about the two free webinars that we held in February and April 2023. On 31st May 2023, directly from our Annual Meeting in Madrid, we held our third START webinar, that we titled "Sustainable Solutions to Unlock the Potential of Thermoelectrics and Secondary Materials". We gathered there most of the speakers, and held the webinar in hybrid format, with about 30 delegates at the meeting physically in the room, and about the same number connected remotely. Thanks to all who took part! This was the agenda of the 3rd START webinar, 31st May 2023, 14:30-17:00 CEST:

- **14:30** Bruno Vicenzi (European Powder Metallurgy Association) and Filipe Neves (LNEG) – Welcome and introduction
- **14:35** Doug Crane (DTP Thermoelectrics, START Scientific Advisory Board) – "Thermoelectric energy harvesting: principles, challenges and opportunities"
- **15:10** Q&A
- **15:20** Julie Hollis (EuroGeoSurveys, START Scientific Advisory Board) – "The role of EuroGeoSurveys in supporting the EU's ambition to boost domestic critical raw materials supply from secondary resources including mine waste"
- **15:55** Q&A
- **16:05** António José (Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe) – "Sulphidic mining waste in Germany"
- **16:15** Piotr Lipiarski (GeoSphere Austria) and Thomas Unterweissacher (Unterweissacher) – "Tennantite and tetrahedrite from two Austrian mine waste sites"
- **16:25** Concepción Fernández Leyva (IGME-CSIC) – "Tetrahedrite Deposits in Spain"
- **16:35** Stanislav Šoltés (Štátny geologický ústav Dionýza Štúra) – "Tetrahedrites from Mária Mine, Rožňava, Slovakia"
- **16:45** Q&A
- **17:00** End of webinar

After the event, we split the long session video into 3 parts, that are D. Crane's, J. Hollis's, and the START speakers, respectively. You can find all these videos in our [Multimedia](#) page of the website, where you can also find the previous webinars' footage!

Figure 10 - Doug Crane (DTP Thermoelectrics) presenting in the 3rd START webinar.

START INTERNAL LCA WORKSHOP

In June 2023 the partner 3drivers presented to the Consortium an online workshop dedicated to life cycle assessment (LCA). The session was divided in two parts, the first one with the theoretical introduction to LCA methodology (available for public dissemination¹⁴), and the second one to perform a LCA practical example in SimaPro software, to gather initial insights of ThermoElectric Generator (TEG) use case and to demonstrate what the LCA work would be for the project (exclusively for the START partners).

The main objectives of the LCA workshop were to:

- Understand what LCA is and how it is conducted;
- Understand the type of data needed;
- Get to know existing tools;
- Define the objective and scope;
- Define the functional unit;
- Develop data inventories for materials and processes;
- Quantify the environmental impacts;
- Interpret the results;
- Understand why it is important to take a whole-life approach to calculate environmental impact;
- Develop LCA with a practical example: ex. what is the stage with the greatest impact and possible mitigation strategies.

Several topics were addressed, including:

- 1) LCA within Industrial Ecology tools ;
- 2) Standards;
- 3) Structure of a process-based LCA model;
- 4) LCA terminology (ISO 14040:2006);
- 5) LCA main stages;
- 6) Principles of LCA;
- 7) When LCA could be useful;
- 8) When LCA should not be used;
- 9) LCA resources;
- 10) Goal and scope definition;
- 11) Inventory analysis;
- 12) Impact assessment;
- 13) Interpretation of results;

Figure 90: START-Newsletter_Issue_3-page-013

In the practical session it was possible to get knowledge of TEG complete life cycle stages, from the raw materials extraction, production processes, use stage, to the end-of-life. This was an important preparation for the LCA work to be developed in START context, namely for the definition of the functional unit, and the goal and scope, and also to specify the data required to build the inventory of the inputs from natural resources, the technological sphere (materials, fuels, energy), the outputs (wastes, emissions), and the avoided products (e. g., minerals from recovered tailings, energy produced from waste heat) of the TEG device. The LCA analysis will assess the environmental benefits of START's TEG device in comparison to other synthetic-based devices, in order to demonstrate the sustainability of the product developed from mine tailings.

START LECTURED AT THE 21ST EPMA SUMMER SCHOOL IN DRESDEN, 21ST JULY 2023

The EPMA Powder Metallurgy Summer School¹⁶ is organised by the European Powder Metallurgy Association (EPMA) with support from its members. The PM Summer Schools gives young scientists and engineers advanced teaching of PM's advantages and limitations by some of the leading academic and industrial personnel in Europe. Since 1998, about 1000 young graduates from both industry and academia from all over Europe have attended these summer schools. The 2023 edition, the 21st in the series, was held in Dresden, Germany, from 17th to 21st July. 59 trainees took part.

START was briefly presented by B. Vicenzi (EPMA) during his opening speech on Monday 17th July, as happened in 2022 in the 20th edition in Ciudad Real (Spain). Among the several lectures there were topics that are relevant for START ("Powder Manufacturing and Characterization", "Alternative Methods and Innovative Sintering"), but especially on the project's side on Friday 21st, 13:00 – 13:30, A. Bianchin (MBN) closed the lectures by giving a presentation titled "Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project".

START will feature again in the 22nd edition that will take place in Alessandria (Italy) in July 2024, possibly in a new format, as a lab experience.

Figure 11 - Highlights of the START project presented by B. Vicenzi of EPMA during the opening presentation at the 21st EPMA PM Summer School in Dresden, Germany

Figure 12 - A. Bianchin (MBN) presenting "Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project" at the 21st EPMA PM Summer School in Dresden, Germany.

Figure 13 - A. Bianchin (MBN) presenting "Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project" at the 21st EPMA PM Summer School in Dresden, Germany.

START LECTURED AT THE 2ND EDITION OF SUMMER SCHOOL “MATERIALS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION” IN PORTO, 7TH SEPTEMBER 2023

An oral presentation entitled “Projeto START - Utilização de tetraedrites como material termoelétrico” (“START Project – Use of tetraedrites as thermoelectric material”) was given by José Brito Correia to 20 Portuguese PhD and Master’s students in the session dedicated to “Advanced Energy Materials” at the 2nd edition of the “Materials for Energy Transition” Summer School. This was a three-day event organised by Sociedade Portuguesa de Materiais (SPM), Ordem dos Engenheiros Região Norte, INL and LNEG. This was an excellent opportunity to publicize the project’s activities among the student community, with a more pedagogical presentation on mechanochemical synthesis, spark plasma sintering and the use of tetraedrites for thermoelectric applications. At the end of the session Filipe Neves participated in the round table where he had the opportunity to frame the project’s objectives within the current challenges associated with the energy transition and the indispensable contribution of materials.

Figure 14 - Presentation by José Brito Correia (LNEG) at the 2nd edition of the Summer School “Materials For Energy Transition” in Porto, 7th September 2023.

Figure 15 - Round table including Filipe Neves (LNEG) at the 2nd edition of the Summer School “Materials For Energy Transition” in Porto, 7th September 2023.

OTHER START DISSEMINATION EVENTS

ASGMI Webinar “Copper Geology in Latin America”, 27th-28th September

The webinar “Copper Geology in Ibero-America”, presented by the Ibero-American Geological and Mining Services Association (ASGMI) and organized by its “Expert Group on Metallogeny and Mineral Resources” took place on the 27th and 28th of September at 13:00 (GMT) through Google Meet. The objective of the webinar was to inform about different aspects of the copper mining industry, given the fact that copper is rapidly becoming a very demanded material due to the changes in energy and transportation models.

The webinar featured prestigious speakers from different Ibero-American countries, who talked about topics like copper deposits in different parts of Ibero-America, the geology of said deposits and uses of the mineral.

Ester Boixereu, from the Geological and Mining Institute of Spain (IGME), gave her presentation “Reaprovechamiento de pasivos ambientales de la minería del cobre. El caso del proyecto START” (“Reuse of environmental liabilities from copper mining. The case of the START project”). Her presentation, as well as the rest of the webinar, can be found here: <https://youtu.be/PFpbmHLTpDQ> (in Spanish).

Figure 16 - Two moments from the presentation by Ester Bolxereu (IGME) during the ASGM Webinar "Copper Geology in Latin America".

START in 2023 European Researchers' Night Events

The START project was featured in the MacaroniNight 2023 digital EU Corner and the physical EU Corners in Tenerife on the 29th September 2023 and was featured in the Patent's Week (2nd-6th October) in Gran Canaria under the umbrella of the European Researchers Night of the Macaronesia. Copies of Starty's comics were printed by LPRC and distributed. Here are some data of the event:

- Digital EU Corner: 52.800 views
- EU Corner Tenerife: 3.000 participants – 400 comics copies
- Patents Week Gran Canaria: 500 participants – 100 comics copies
- Upcoming social media campaign highlighting the projects November to December

START also took part in the European Researchers Night (also on 29th September) in Lisbon.

Figure 17 - In the "MacaroniNight", START material was distributed.

Figure 18 - START at the European Researchers Night in Lisbon.

**EURO
PM2023**
CONGRESS & EXHIBITION

EPMA
EUROPEAN POWDER METALLURGY ASSOCIATION
1 - 4 October 2023
LISBON

Booth and presentations at Euro PM2023 in Lisbon, Portugal, 01-04 October 2023

The European Powder Metallurgy Association (EPMA) hosted this year its annual European Congress & Exhibition in Lisbon, from 1st to 4th October²². About 800 delegates could follow a plenary session, about 70 technical sessions and visit the exhibition with more than 80 exhibitors.

Among the booths, START organised one with informative posters and banners, a collection of exhibits (minerals, powders, an example of thermoelectric generator device) and a screen where the START introductory video and the latest Starty comic strip with explanations about the role of the project in pursuing the objectives of the EU in terms of efficient use of resources were displayed.

Figure 19 - The START booth at the Euro PM2023 Congress & Exhibition in Lisbon.

Figure 20 - The display with samples and the screen with the running Starty comics.

Figure 21 - Demonstration of the START project to students of the Young Engineers programme during Euro PM2023, by J.B. Correia (LNEG)

In the morning of Tuesday 3rd October, four twenty-minute demonstrations of the START project were held by José Brito Correia (LNEG) for international doctoral and master's students at the project booth. The attendees were participants of the EPMA's Young Engineers programme²³: 48 students were hosted free of charge in the first 2 days of the congress and were given introductory lectures and a guided tour in the exhibition, including the START booth. These demonstrations featured a general description of the project and the presentation of materials and devices within the scope of thermoelectric materials, arousing great interest on the part of the students.

On Tuesday afternoon, at 16:30, a 30' oral presentation entitled "Replacement of tellurium in thermoelectric materials" was given by José Brito Correia in Session 44, the Functional Materials Special Interest Seminar – "Sustainability of Critical Raw Materials by PM".

Figure 22 - Presentation of J.B. Correia (LNEG) in Session 44: Functional Materials Special Interest Seminar – "Sustainability of Critical Raw Materials by PM", during the Euro PM2023.

In addition to these specific activities, the two Technical Managers of EPMA B. Vicenzi and K. Boz, gave short introductions to the project during the 6 Sectoral Group meetings (EuroAM, EuroFM, EuroMIM, Euro Press&Sinter, EuroHM, EuroHIP) and a Working Group meeting (EHQS) held in the Congress.

Future events

START is organizing participation in several more events in the next months. At the moment, we are focusing on three upcoming events.

On 30th-31st October, G. Olivenza of ASGMI will give a presentation about START titled "Reusing Secondary Mineral Resources For The Energy Transition: The Project Start Example" at the European Union SuperCluster Lapland Geoconference in Rovaniemi, Finland. It will be a great opportunity for our project to show our approach to similar projects and thus especially for our "clustering" effort for synergies.

In November, ASGMI is expected to hold its in-person workshop on mining environmental liabilities in Brazil. We are currently awaiting official confirmation from the Brazilian Geological Service regarding the event's dates, and location. Some representatives of START will be present and will likely be able to present our activity there.

Also in November, namely on 13-17 November 2023, the 8th edition of the Raw Materials Week in Brussels will see START participating with some members and dissemination materials (poster, video).

More events will come after these!

If you are from a similar initiative or project and would like to organise something together, please contact us! We have a specific line of activity on "clustering" with initiatives that share one or more topics with us, so that would be very welcome.

TECHNICAL PILLS

DESIGNING OPTIMAL THERMOELECTRIC SULPHIDES

The interdependence of α , σ , and κ has led to design strategies to maximize zT by seeking to decouple the critical connection between electronic and thermal transport:

- **Enhancing $\alpha^2\sigma$:** Solid solutions often show multiband behavior with valleys around the Fermi level, a fingerprint of TE efficiency. Band engineering approaches can move these bands toward their respective edges, leading to reduced energy differences that offer many conducting channels. Methods like band convergence and nestification are usually utilized for increased degeneracy, and extra effective density of states near the band edge regions result also in enhanced Seebeck coefficient. Furthermore, deliberate introduction of ionized impurities, to scatter preferentially low-energy charge carriers (energy filtering), increases $\alpha^2\sigma$ when the reduction in carrier mobility is more than compensated by an increase in Seebeck coefficient.
- **Decreasing κ_{ph} :** In most semiconductors thermal conductivity is dominated by the phonon contribution, so materials with low lattice thermal conductivity are sought. The high polarizability of the sulfide anion leads to significant bonding anisotropy, leading to the adoption of low-dimensional structures, which can reduce the lattice contribution to thermal conductivity as well as enhance the Seebeck coefficient. Solid solutions can also dramatically reduce the lattice thermal conductivity, i.e., disturbance of short-range order tends to scatter phonons, while maintenance of long-range order leaves the charge carrier mobility largely unaffected. Furthermore, the lattice thermal conductivity can be decreased by reducing the crystal size since a substantial fraction of heat is carried by low frequency phonons, and these are prone to scattering at grain boundaries.

The above strategies instigate the systematic exploration of diversified substitutions, but only a minute fraction of sulfide compositions has been scrutinized and through rather conservative and isoelectronic alloying strategies, although more exotic substitutions can lead to high power factors. Stability at the operating temperatures is mandatory in TE applications, and natural substitutions in minerals formed at high temperatures hint at stable configurations. The concept of maximizing configurational entropy to enhance solid-state miscibility inspires the exploration of unfamiliar composition spaces, but most studies focus on metal alloys and oxides and limited work has been carried out on medium- and high-entropy sulfides. In addition to solid solutions at transition metal sites, incorporation of Sn, present in tetrahedrite, as well as partial substitution of S by Se are potentially beneficial.

Charge carrier concentration and phonon vibrational properties can be designed from first principles. The temperature-dependent TE behavior can then be predicted by solving the Boltzmann transport equation. Efficient first-principles techniques based on density functional theory (DFT) are currently employed for high-throughput theoretical studies. The large quantity of data generated by these studies motivates the use of machine-learning techniques to explore TE properties in vast composition spaces.

Figure 23 - Modification of (a) band valleys (CBM = Conduction Band Minimum energy, VBM = Valence Band Maximum energy), (b) density of states and (c) corresponding $\alpha^2\sigma$ through electronic band structure engineering (adapted from [23]).

MEET THE SCIENTIFIC ADVISORY BOARD MEMBERS: JEAN-YVES ESCABASSE

In the last Issue we have started to present you the members of our Scientific Advisory Board by short interviews where they highlight their activity and the activity of their institutions and companies. Today you will read about Jean-Yves Escabasse.

Figure 24 - Jean-Yves Escabasse is a Chemical Engineer and Doctor, with 40 years of experience in R&D and innovation within several materials industry sectors, with positions held in companies and research institutes, and responsibilities in product and process development, team management, regulatory affairs, IPR issues, sales and marketing, large project management. Coordinator for many multinational projects, in particular "H2020-IND-CE-2016-17/H2020-NMBP-PILOTS-2016 INTEGRAL: Initiative to bring the 2nd generation of ThermoElectric Generators into industrial ReALity (GA 720878, 2016-2019).

Jean-Yves, we understand that since the beginning of your career you have always been involved in R&D and specifically in European research programmes. How would you rate the quality of EU support to its research, development, and innovation entities and to companies' efforts in the field?

Yes, I've been working in Research and Technical Organisations (RTOs) for more than 30 years. EU support through various instruments, in particular Horizon Europe, is essential to foster innovation in Europe. European funding programmes are looked at with much envy across the World. This is emphasised by the long list of third countries requesting to be associated to Horizon Europe. I won't comment much on basic research, which by nature

can almost only be funded publicly, or, as seen in a few countries, by patronage. What disturbs me with such private sponsoring is the research agenda being set by individuals whose (high) merit is to be wealthy. It's most honourable from them to invest their fortune in public interest causes, but the development of the knowledge base of humanity should belong to public authorities and not rely on charity. Regarding applied research, i.e., medium-to-high TRL activities, experience and reason tell me that its funding must be founded on three equal-value pillars. As this R&D work is meant to be transferred to and exploited by industry, industry itself must pay part of it, either in-kind or in-cash; the second pillar is made of public-funded projects, e.g., Horizon Europe. These two sources of funding for RTOs are essential and must be acquired by intensive commercial activities. Both are extremely and rightly competitive, as it is fair that only the best projects must be selected. However, this does not suffice. RTOs cannot be 100% funded by public or private contracts and a fair share of public, basic, automatic funding is necessary, e.g., as a government grant. This is the financial model of large RTOs such as CEA, Fraunhofer and VTT, in particular. Ideally each pillar should represent one third, but unfortunately government funding is lower than that and this is one of the reasons why Europe does not invest the intended 3% of GDP in R&D and innovation. The other reason is the chronic under-investment of industry in own R&D activities.

Is Horizon Europe achieving its declared objectives, according to you? What would be your suggestions for improvements for the next framework?

This is a difficult question. Horizon Europe is undeniably very ambitious and has noble goals. There is an old saying to the effect that you should not bite more than you can chew. An unwanted effect could be to spread its aid too thinly. This is probably the result of a complex and lengthy elaboration and approval process of Framework Programmes by the triangular loop Commission/Member-States Council/Parliament. In effect, lobbyists and budgetary or political considerations take precedence, maybe in opposition to real needs of the Research and Innovation community. I noted that the Commission has now for several years developed Public Private Partnerships under several collaboration models: co-funded, co-programmed or joint undertakings. The last two largely involve industry participation, both in financial commitment and technical inputs. To me, this is a very strong point for the relevance of work programmes and project topics, at least in Pillar 2 of Horizon Europe.

Europe is facing a growing challenge in securing the supply of critical raw materials (CRMs) that are essential for its green and digital transitions. In your opinion what are the potential impacts of the CRM supply challenge on the achievement of the EU's climate and energy goals?

Climate change is a tremendous challenge for the whole mankind. If you look at it, the use of fossil energies is a major cause. Other greenhouse gases than CO₂ are also strong contributors and should be dealt with, e.g., methane emissions by cattle or fluorinated compounds in various applications, but this is not the topic here. Take it or leave it, we must urgently cut our CO₂ emissions worldwide, lest our planet becomes unliveable. Now what does it mean? One third of CO₂ emissions in the most advanced countries (Western World + BRICS + a couple of others) is caused by the transport sector, where an obvious solution to replacing fossil fuels is electrification. Another third is caused by heating and cooling. Unlike what some activists try to impose, I don't believe that humans will forgo the benefits of technical progress and are prepared to go back to pre-industrial conditions of life. Therefore, it's unrealistic to think that energy demand can be drastically reduced. Most advanced countries must indeed save energy, but developing countries have a legitimate claim to using more energy. In this context, global energy demand cannot and will not decrease. This means that more, but cleaner energy must be produced, and it must be used more sustainably.

Regarding production, CO₂ emission-free energy is either nuclear (by fission, until fusion becomes reality) or renewable (solar, wind, hydraulic...). Most renewable energies are intermittent, so to dispose of continuous power supply, pilotable sources are unavoidable. If you want to avoid coal, gas or fuel, this means nuclear. All these need critical metals: uranium as nuclear fuels, rare earths for magnets in power generators (windmills and others), e-motors (vehicles, robotics and machinery in industry), lithium and graphite in batteries, ultra-pure silicon and silver in solar panels, platinum group metals in fuel cells and electrolyzers, nickel and cobalt everywhere to quote only the main ones.

The digital transition has the same consequence: more computers, more chips in cars, in manufacturing equipment, in domotics, everywhere, mean more silicon and doping materials of high purity.

So, if we really want to achieve the EU's climate and energy goals, we must massively electrify transport, industry and domestic usage. This means that we all need critical metals in high amounts, while Europe cannot fulfil its needs easily. Market demands are here, mines and conversion are elsewhere. We have the following options:

- **Forego:** I don't believe that we can altogether forego transport, lighting, domestic comfort, but we must in any case dramatically reduce energy consumption in all domains. This belongs to individual and collective behaviour, worldwide.

- **Reduce:** Naturally, industry offers electrified products with highest performance, for example driving range for e-cars, based on high-capacity batteries and high-efficiency e-motors. But do we really need a 3-tonne SUV with 500 km range to drive most of the time in town and go to work or shopping? Lower performance means dramatically reduced needs for Critical Raw Materials (CRMs). Modesty can perhaps avoid us complete forbearance. Here again a matter of behaviour. Reducing the market demand means frugality. You can also reduce the technical demand by a better use of the same materials: this belongs to science. Material research can provide technologies where a reduced amount of CRMs can achieve the same performance, e.g., grain boundary diffusion of dysprosium in RE magnets. There's still a high potential in this field.
- **Substitute:** again, this is a matter of scientific research. For instance, Nd or Pr can be replaced by La or Ce with almost the same performance. These are indeed CRMs, but far more abundant and cheaper than Nd or Pr. So, substitution + modesty (accept a slightly reduced performance) can be a solution. In addition, research can discover new materials to complement those already known and needed for the transition, but this will take time, a lot of time.
- **Recycle:** obviously, what you get from end-of-life products needn't be supplied from primary sources, e.g., mining. However, considering the tremendous rise in demand, this will help but not suffice. Primary materials will always be needed, so recycling alone can't be the solution.

To conclude, yes, the access to CRMs is instrumental in Europe's achievements. To be frank, I have doubts that we can make it in time, unless we do a lot of "foregoing".

Since 2016 you are with CEA in Grenoble, France, and when you joined you have been involved in a H2020 project named INTEGRAL, whose subject was actually thermoelectricity. Can you tell us more about it?

INTEGRAL was about upscaling second-generation of improved thermoelectric materials, mainly based on silicides and half-Heuslers: affordable and mostly based on earth-abundant elements and eco-friendly materials, in order to address mass-market needs (automotive, heavy-duty trucks, autonomous temperature control and industry waste heat recovery). INTEGRAL would allow the industry to step up towards advanced manufacturing and commercialisation of systems integrating multifunctional TE materials, through material customisation, in particular using a nano-based approach, latest techniques for characterization and process control as well as up-scaled pilot-line demonstrations. Ambitious goals had been set for performance, production scale and costs. Technically, things went well, and we were indeed able to carry out successfully most foreseen demonstrations in relevant or even industrial environment, especially in industrial waste heat harvesting.

Figure 98: START-Newsletter_Issue_3-page-021

However, in the automotive (petrol engine, passenger vehicle) and transport (long haul diesel truck) sectors, we were faced with too low temperature difference and thermal transfer on the hot side, leading to disappointing efficiencies. As a matter of fact, Internal Combustion Engines (ICEs) have become so efficient that the temperature of exhaust gases is too low to operate TEGs efficiently. To make it short, considering the price of fuel at the time and the cost of the TEGs compared with the harvested power, it wasn't worth it. What killed the game was the diesel-gate crisis in 2015, where Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs, car makers) took it seriously and suddenly turned their interest towards electric vehicles. Nowadays, all investments by OEMs go in this direction and they have no interest in TEGs in ICE vehicles. So, I don't see any future there.

How do you see thermoelectric devices in the rush towards energy efficiency and cleaner production? Do you foresee good opportunities in some sectors in the near future?

In addition to what I concluded about INTEGRAL, above, I think that any process that requires high temperatures or involves very hot sources may benefit from energy harvesting: metal industries, glass, cement, ceramic industries, and also domestic heating at small-home, family-home or collective-home levels. When in winter, everyone wants to be warm and comfortable at home, they push either their boiler (whether with oil, gas, or wood) or their heat pumps, or both. Any kWh that's produced at home with a TEG coupled with the boiler can be fed directly to the heat pump or sold to the grid. Combined heat-and-power, though conceptualised many years ago, just makes sense!

Now, there are challenges, which need to be tackled to make TEGs reliable and efficient. As I earlier mentioned, thermal transfer is essential, and this is true for both hot and cold sides. Not only you need good heat exchangers, but also good conductivity at the interfaces. Architecture of devices and systems is pivotal, and there's a lot of work to

do in this field. Next, TEGs are by essence working under thermal gradients and if you want a good thermodynamic yield, you need a high temperature difference. This causes important thermomechanical constraints on materials with different coefficients of thermal expansion. Not the least of the challenges is cycling. Most of the time, TEGs will be used intermittently, meaning that the hot side will alternatively become very hot and back to cold while the cold side will not change that much. This means fatigue on the materials (TE materials are generally brittle) and on the interfaces. Looking into the literature and on what's presented in TE conferences, a lot of research is made on materials to increase zT , which indeed makes sense, but I have the feeling that researchers tend to neglect challenges of assembling those materials into modules, devices and systems.

You have seen what START is trying to do in the field of thermoelectricity, mine waste recovery and waste heat recovery. What are, in your view, the strongest features of our project?

Mankind has lived in abundance for centuries, but now this is over. Cheap oil, coal, gas and mineral-rich ores led us to pick only the best and most accessible resources and through away the rest, like torching gas in oil wells and extracting only the most valuable ores in mines, while throwing away tailings rich with other elements. The current change of paradigm leads us to think better. Extracting tetrahedrites for mine waste is one good example, and I like the idea of coupling it with another tapping in wasted resources, namely heat. Static conversion such as TEGs have this benefit of easily producing electricity from heat that would otherwise be thrown away. In that sense, START is a very good idea. However, in order to make thermoelectricity work, don't forget that many other technical challenges must be solved.

Thanks Jean-Yves!

Figure 25 - The INTEGRAL Horizon 2020 project ("Initiative to bring the 2nd generation of ThermoElectric Generators into Industrial ReALity"^[2]) was led by CEA (France) and carried out between December 2016 and November 2019.

Figure 99: START-Newsletter_Issue_3-page-022

CONSORTIUM TOUR

We continue our tour of consortium members: in this Issue, meet ASGMI (Spain) and GeniCore (Poland).

ASGMI - ASSOCIATION OF IBEROAMERICAN GEOLOGICAL AND MINING SURVEYS

ASGMI
Asociación de Servicios
de Geología y Minería
Iberoamericanas

ASGMI, the Association of Iberoamerican Geological and Mining Surveys is a non-profit organization founded on 1993 which represents twenty-two National Geological Surveys in Latin-America, Portugal and Spain. It has its own legal entity since 2012, and it is currently formed by twelve groups of experts dedicated to different areas of Geoscientific knowledge. The main mission of ASGMI is:

To generate and disseminate geoscientific knowledge to contribute to the socioeconomic development of society by horizontal, bilateral and multilateral cooperation between the associated members.

- To provide international, scientific and technical cooperation focused on development, but considering society's growing concerns about natural disasters, management of mineral, hydric and energetic resources, pollution and climate change effects.

- The institutional strengthening of the associated Geological and Mining Services.

The main activities of ASGMI consist of monthly meetings of expert groups that collaborate on tasks related to projects funded by the European Union in which ASGMI participates or ASGMI projects that include initiatives such as the development of the recently published "Geochemical Sampling Manual" or the "Critical Minerals Map of Latin America" currently being developed by the Mineral Resources Expert Group. In addition to ASGMI's annual in-person General Assembly, the organization hosts thematic workshops, both in-person and virtual, open to the entire scientific community.

Inside START, ASGMI cooperates in different parts of the project. Through its Group of Experts in Mining Environmental Liabilities, ASGMI participates in the selection of mine waste sites and physical separation and concentration of minerals. (WP2).

ASGMI also participates in the Communication and Dissemination work package (WP6) of the project, collaborating in the management of information on SlideShare and in the communication and dissemination of technical and scientific information related to the project at various events and initiatives in which ASGMI is involved. ASGMI leads the clustering task, with objective is to identify similar projects to establish synergies and carry out joint communication efforts. Additionally, ASGMI is responsible for organizing a training workshop open to Bachelor's and Master's degree students, where they can interact with researchers, ask questions, and learn more about the project.

<https://asgmi.org>

Figure 100: START-Newsletter_Issue_3-page-023

GENICORE

GeniCore

Genius at the Core

What is GeniCore and U-FAST?

GeniCore is a pioneering company in the field of material engineering, specializing in the manufacturing of Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS) machines. These machines are designed for sintering a broad range of innovative powder materials and applications. One of GeniCore's standout products is the U-FAST system. This system is engineered to generate current pulses with the shortest rise time available in the market. The U-FAST system can sinter materials either without grain growth or with limited grain growth, thanks to its unique design that optimizes the connection between the power supply and the stamps. This not only enhances the machine's performance but also significantly reduces power consumption.

What is Pulse Plasma Compaction (PPC)?

Pulse Plasma Compaction (PPC) is an advanced form of the conventional Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS) process. PPC employs high voltage and short electrical pulses to achieve full densification of materials at lower temperatures. This is particularly useful for sintering sulphide-based powders. The technology offers several advantages over traditional SPS, including faster heating rates, more accurate control of sintering energy, and higher levels of safety and reliability. PPC is a modification of the conventional SPS process, where energy stored in a capacitor bank is delivered to the powder in short pulses. This field-enhanced diffusivity enables full densification at lower temperature setpoints than in conventional SPS.

How is GeniCore Contributing to the START Project?

GeniCore's innovative PPC and U-FAST technologies are playing a crucial role in the START project. These technologies are expected to bring about significant improvements in material density and stability. This is particularly beneficial for the performance of thermoelectric (TE) materials used in the project. The START project aims to leverage these technologies to prevent thermally induced solid-state reactions in TE materials, thereby enhancing their overall performance. The production of square samples in place of traditional cylindrical compacts will also be assessed, representing a cost-effective solution and a huge step forward in the consolidation of parallelepiped thermoelements required for device assembly.

Figure 101: START-Newsletter_Issue_3-page-024

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ¹Römer, F. and Goldmann, D. 2019, Wiederaufbereitung eines bergbaulichen Abfalls im Harz – Wie aus Altlasten in Zukunft vielleicht Lagerstätten werden., CHEMKON 2019, 26, 66. DOI: 10.1002/ckon.201800080
- ²Schirmer, T., Römer, F., Elwert, T., Goldmann, D., Characterization of tailings of the Rammelsberg ore deposit for a potential reprocessing. Proceedings of the 9th European Metallurgical conference, EMC 2017, 25-28 June 2017, www.scopus.com
- ³German mine waste cadastre for metal raw materials (under development, BGR, Hannover, stand 01.09.2023);
- ⁴The online database <http://www.mindat.org> and references therein, accessed in May 2023
- ⁵The online database www.mineralienatlas.de and references therein
- ⁶The online database de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Liste_von_stillgelegten_Bergwerken_in_Deutschland and references therein
- ⁷Google Maps, maps.google.com
- ⁸Fritsche, R. and Schmidt, J., 1996, Bestandsaufnahme von Rückstandshalden aus Bergbau und Erzaufbereitung in Baden-Württemberg: Forschungszentrum Karlsruhe, Technik und Umwelt, Band II: Mittlerer Teil, FZKA 5769B, <https://publikationen.bibliothek.kit.edu/270040565/3813594>
- ⁹Metz, R., 1988, Historischer Atlas von Baden-Württemberg XI, 10. https://www.leo-bw.de/media/kgf_atlas/current/delivered/pdf/HABW_11_10.pdf
- ¹⁰Metz, R., Richter, M., Schürenberg, H., 1957. Die Blei-Zink-Erzgänge des Schwarzwaldes. Beiheft. Geol. Jahrb. 29, 277
- ¹¹Walter, B.F., Mathias Burisch, Tobias Fusswinkel, Michael A.W. Marks, Matthew Steele-Macinnis, Markus Wälle, Olga B. Apukhtina, Gregor Markl, 2018, Multi-reservoir fluid mixing processes in rift-related hydrothermal veins, Schwarzwald, SW-Germany, Journal of Geochemical Exploration, 186, 158-186, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jexplo.2017.12.004>
- ¹²Werner, W. and Dennert, V., 2004, Lagerstätten und Bergbau im Schwarzwald, LGRB, Freiburg, ISBN 2-00-014636-9
- ¹³https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Density_functional_theory
- ¹⁴The maximum efficiency of the energy conversion process (for both power generation and cooling) at a given temperature point in the material is determined by the thermoelectric materials figure of merit zT , given by [Equation], where σ is the electrical conductivity, κ the thermal conductivity, S is the Seebeck coefficient, all functions of absolute temperature T .
- ¹⁵Available in <https://www.start-heproject.com/multimedia/>
- ¹⁶<https://summerschool.epma.com/>
- ¹⁷<https://europm2023.com/>
- ¹⁸<https://www.youngengineers.epma.com/>
- ¹⁹N. Wang, M. Li, H. Xiao, Z. Gao, Z. Liu, X. Zu, S. Li, L. Qiao, npj Comput Mater 7 (2021) 18
- ²⁰<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/720878>

CONTACTS

START regularly updates its website and social media with news about its activities, but also with more general documents and info on the topics of relevance for the project. Thermoelectricity, waste heat recovery, mine waste remining, sustainability, raw materials and critical raw materials, energy efficiency, and many others.

If you are interested in receiving this newsletter and other special news from the project directly in your mailbox, consider subscribing our mailing list on the website ("Contacts" page, "subscribe" section)! Clicking on the "Subscribe" button, you will fill a form generated by SendinBlue, our mailing system, and will subsequently receive an E-Mail to confirm your address. Your data will be treated and stored in accordance with the EU GDPR Regulation. And do not forget to follow all our social media accounts! Here is the list of the important links to click to reach our news:

Website: <https://www.start-heproject.com/>

Twitter: https://twitter.com/START_HEproject

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/86266991/>

Twitch: https://www.twitch.tv/start_he_project

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCHVjEhpVz9uaEgzlCj2InPA>

SlideShare: <https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/>

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Figure 102: START-Newsletter_Issue_3-page-025

11 ANNEX II – START ARTICLE ON “CIÊNCIA & TECNOLOGIA DOS MATERIAIS” 2023 VOL.35 Nº1

SPM Sociedade Portuguesa de Materiais

85

PROJETO START – SUSTAINABLE ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS BASED ON INNOVATIVE MINE WASTE RECYCLING

START é um projeto de Inovação cofinanciado pelo programa Horizonte Europa da União Europeia (UE) no âmbito do cluster 4: Digital, Indústria e Espaço. O principal objetivo do projeto START é o de criar uma cadeia de valor sustentável e um ecossistema de inovação associados ao desenvolvimento de geradores termoeletrônicos (TE) sem telúrio, constituídos por semicondutores do tipo-p produzidos através da utilização direta de minério à base de tetraedrite, recolhido em escombros de minas. Esta solução tecnológica tem assim o potencial de promover a redução, simultaneamente, da dependência da UE em matérias-primas importadas e do desperdício no uso dos seus recursos, em linha com as prioridades do Pacto Ecológico Europeu e com o Plano de Ação para as Matérias-Primas Críticas.

DESCRIÇÃO GERAL DO PROJETO START Orçamento, duração e consórcio

Com um orçamento total 9 194 441.25 €, o projeto START arrancou as suas atividades em Junho de 2022 e tem uma duração de 48 meses. O Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia, I.P. (LNEG, Portugal) é a instituição coordenadora do consórcio constituído por 15 instituições, de 10 estados membros da UE e de 1 país associado (Fig. 1), onde se incluem 6 organizações de investigação com forte formação e conhecimento nas áreas da geologia, da ciência dos materiais e das energias renováveis, 7 PME's que garantem toda a cadeia de valor, desde a produção, exploração e avaliação da pegada ecológica, e 2 associações internacionais sem fins lucrativos com uma rede consolidada de parceiros e stakeholders.

Fig. 1 – Membros do consórcio do projeto START e destaque dos países que eles representam.

Motivação

A mudança climática é um dos maiores desafios enfrentados pela humanidade. O combate ao aquecimento global depende da rápida implementação de uma transição verde com a qual a União Europeia (UE) está totalmente comprometida por meio do Pacto Ecológico Europeu.

A transição verde assenta numa mudança de sistemas de energia baseados no uso intensivo de combustíveis fósseis para sistemas de energia envolvendo a utilização intensiva de materiais o que implica uma maior necessidade de recursos minerais. Esta crescente procura por minerais essenciais, e a diminuição da qualidade dos minérios, tem conduzido a um aumento substancial nos volumes de resíduos das explorações mineiras. Assim, a utilização de resíduos de minas como matérias-primas secundárias para o desenvolvimento de dispositivos avançados de conversão de energia representa um forte incentivo económico e de proteção ambiental.

Por outro lado, estima-se que cerca de dois terços da energia primária produzida em todo o mundo é perdida na forma de calor residual. O aproveitamento adequado desse calor residual e a sua conversão direta em energia elétrica através da utilização geradores TE tem o potencial de melhorar a eficiência energética, por exemplo de processo industriais, e evitar dezenas de milhões de toneladas de emissões de CO₂. Contudo, os atuais geradores TE comerciais têm por base materiais à base de telúrio, que é um elemento derivado de recursos minerais escassos na Europa, tornando o continente fortemente dependente de importações.

Objetivo e impacto

Neste contexto, o projeto START propõe uma solução tecnológica assente na conversão de resíduos mineiros em materiais para recuperação de calor residual sem telúrio (Fig. 2). Tal será obtido através da produção de materiais TE do tipo p que incorporem sulfuretos descartados em resíduos mineiros, e que atualmente representam um risco ambiental tais como

DISSEMINAÇÃO DE PROJETOS I&DT

Figure 103: START article on “Ciência & Tecnologia Dos Materiais” 2023 Vol.35 Nº1, p. 85.

os pertencentes aos da série tetraedrita-tenantite ($\text{Cu}_6[\text{Cu}_4(\text{TM})_2](\text{Sb,As})_4\text{S}_{13}$, onde TM = metal de transição), para substituir os atuais materiais TE comerciais do tipo p à base de telúrio.

Fig. 2 – Conceito da ideia central do projeto START: transformar resíduos mineiros em materiais para recuperação de calor residual.

Esta abordagem do projeto START contribui assim para uma utilização eficiente dos recursos ao mesmo tempo que incentiva a produção de energia verde por meio de geradores TE, em linha com as estratégias delineadas no Pacto Ecológico Europeu e nos Planos de Ação da UE para as Matérias-Primas Críticas e para a Economia Circular.

Os principais resultados esperados são:

- Cadeia de valor inovadora: o projeto START propõe tecnologias disruptivas para uso direto de minerais em ecossistemas de energia renovável termoelétrica, tendo por base a transformação de resíduos mineiros em materiais para recuperação de calor residual.
- Nova oportunidade de mercado para os recursos minerais Europeus: convertendo recursos secundários descartados e disponíveis na Europa em matérias-primas secundárias de elevado valor acrescentado.
- Reforçar a competitividade da UE em matéria de recursos: a reciclagem de resíduos de minas contribuirá para a segurança do aprovisionamento de matérias-primas e para a sustentabilidade Europeia.
- Ecossistemas de energia renovável: o projeto START permitirá a transição para uma sociedade e economia mais verdes por meio de ecoinovação, modelos económicos mais sustentáveis e promovendo a segurança energética.
- Novo ecossistema comercial: o projeto START criará um ecossistema comercial de rápido crescimento que atrairá novas partes interessadas explorando oportunidades de mercado para replicação e desenvolvimento de mercado.

O impacto do projeto START para uma UE mais sustentável e resiliente é definido em três pontos:

1. Redução da dependência da UE de matérias-primas críticas primárias.
2. Incentivo à implementação de processos de economia circular.
3. Produção de módulos TE, com impacto no aumento da eficiência global dos sistemas de produção e consumo de energia, bem como na redução das emissões de gases com efeito de estufa.

Como seguir o projeto START

As diferentes atividades do projeto START podem ser seguidas consultando a Newsletter do projeto, intitulada "RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE for a Sustainable Future", a qual é distribuída gratuitamente por email tendo os interessados que fazer a subscrição em <https://www.start-heproject.com/contact/>.

Mais informações sobre o projeto START podem ser obtidas através das seguintes plataformas digitais:

Website: www.start-heproject.com
 LinkedIn: /start-he-project
 Twitter: /START_HEproject

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DISSEMINAÇÃO DE PROJETOS I&DT

Figure 105: START article on “Ciência & Tecnologia Dos Materiais” 2023 Vol.35 Nº1, p. 87.